

CONTRIBUTIONS TO IMPROVE BY PADDOCKING WITH CATTLE OF SUBALPINE GRASSLAND FORM THE BUCEGI MOUNTAINS

Vasile Adrian BLAJ¹, Teodor MARUȘCA^{1,2}, Andreea Cristina ANDREOIU¹,
Marcela Mirela DRAGOȘ¹, Paul Marian ZEVEDEI¹

Abstract

Permanent grasslands from sub-alpine in the Bucegi Massif located at 1800 - 2200 m altitude have resulted after deforestation of spruce groves (Picea abies) and juniper shrubs (Pinus mugo). Mostly of these grasslands are degraded, being invaded by Nardus stricta species, requiring the improvement operations. In this way researches were carried out by paddocking with sheep and less with cattle, during the grazing season. In 2008 it has been setup an experimental field, with the following experimental factors: the intensity of paddocking 0; 2; 4; 6 nights/cow/6 m², herbicide, over-seeding and phosphorus fertilization. In the second stage, in 2013, it was paddocked again with an intensity of 4 nights/cow/6 m², with the purpose to remark the residual effect of improving pasture factors from the first stage. The results highlight the favourable effect for a long period of herbicides, overseeding, phosphorus fertilization and paddocking with cattle on Nardus stricta degraded grasslands. By this method, the degraded grassy carpets have been improved during the first stage by conventional methods, creating optimal conditions for practicing an organic agriculture, after two years of conversion.

Keywords: grasslands of *Nardus stricta* species, herbicides, over-seeding, paddocking with cattle.

INTRODUCTION

For the pastures located in the mountain area or in case of high mountain in subalpine and alpine level, fertilisation by paddocking with sheep and cattle represents the only one and the most efficient method to increase production on an small areas [1] Also, improvement of pastures with degraded cover of *Nardus stricta* species from subalpine level, can be a measure to protection of rare species, meaning that animals can concentrate on improved pastures, while achieving a decrease of grazing pressure in protected zones or even eliminating them from grazing or even eliminate grazing [3].

In the Bucegi Mountains, the first systematic research regarding paddocking on pasture dominated by *Nardus stricta* has been done starting with the year 1952 [6], followed by research regarding overseeding, simultaneously or after paddocking [Marușca și Frame, 2003]. Also, similar research has been conducted

¹ Grassland Research and Development Institute, Brașov (GRDI) Brasov , 5 Cucului Str., 500128, 0268472701; fax 0268475295, www.pajisti-grassland.ro, office@pajisti-grassland.ro

² Academy of Romania Scientists , Splaiul Independenței 54, 050094, Bucharest, Romania

in Țarcu – Godeanu Mountains on 1959 [7], in Portăreasa Mountains from the Masif Iezer-Păpușa, in 1961 [2], at Padiș in the Bihor Mountains [4].

In all this research activity was found efficiency of paddocking with 1 sheep per 1 square meter, during 3 to 6 nights, for increasing the production and quality of grassland invaded by *Nardus stricta* and necessity to practising overseeding on over-paddocked surfaces.

Have not been sufficiently clarified some issues regarding optimal level of paddocking and during of expressions for the effect of improving methods applied.

In this paper we try to contribute with new elements regarding the effect of repeated paddocking applied on surfaces, that was already fertilized with phosphorus, spraying with total herbicides and overseeding.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experience was carried out at the Research Station for Mountain Grasslands from the Bucegi Mountains, at 1.800 m of altitude in subalpine floor on degraded *Nardus stricta* grassland (40% *N. stricta*).

The experiment was a split plot design with three replicate blocks.

Variants of the experience

Factor A - paddocking 1 cow/6m² in years 2008 and 2014, with graduations:

a1 – 2 nights; a2 – 4 nights; a3 – 6 nights;

Factor B - herbicides - with graduations:

b1 – no herbicides; b2 – 5 L/ha glyphosate;

Factor C - phosphorus fertilization, with graduations:

c1 – without fertilisation; c2 – 100 kg/ha P₂O₅;

To these factors is added, like a common treatment, overseeding with a dose of 30 kg/ha and a mixture of perennial grasses and legumes seed consisting of *Festuca pratensis*, Transilvan variety (28%); *Phleum pratense*, Tirom variety (20%); *Lolium perenne*, Marta variety (10%); *Festuca rubra*, Musica, variety (8%); *Lolium multiflorum*, Tirna variety (8%); *Poa pratensis*, Compact variety (4%); *Phalaris arundinacea* Premier variety (2%); *Trifolium pratense*, Pavo variety (8%); *Lotus corniculatus*, Leo variety (8%); *Trifolium repens*, Riesling variety (4%).

In order to determine the green mass production and its quality from each plot were harvested grass samples (1 m²) in the last decade of July or the first decade of August, when grasses were flowering.

The botanical composition was determined using the method for assessing the percentage of participation in the grassy carpet species (KLAPP– ELEMENBERG

method). Feed quality analysis has been carried out in the laboratory of chemistry from GRDI Braşov, using the current methodology.

After sampling the grass, the rest of plot area was grazed and then the soil samples were collected, on depth of 0-15 cm, for determining the agrochemical soil indices and their evolution.

Soil quality analyses were carried out at the Office for Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry Brasov.

The statistical calculation regarding the analysis of variance has been carried out at GRDI Brasov, using the specifically software specific for interpreting of three-factorial experiments placed in subdivided plots.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dry matter yield

Dry matter yield (DM) is directly influenced by the methods of improvement. Thus, the average for the years 2014-2016 is 2.17 t/ha (table 1) with variations from 1.65 t/ha, at a1b1c2 variant, up to 3.06 t/ha at the a3b2c2 variant. Analyzing the influence of factors to improve separately, we can notice that were obtained at factor A – organic fertilisation by paddocking, average yields of 1.77 t/ha at the 2 nights variant and increasing of production with 21% at 4 nights variant and 45% at 6 nights of paddocking. All of these differences are statistically assured as shown in Table 2. Although, eight years have passed since the factor herbicide was applied, it can be noted that in the 2014-2016 years, average of dry matter production was 8% higher, the differences being statistically assured (table 3).

Table 1. **The average of dry matter yield depending on variants of improvement and years of harvest**

Blana Bucegi, 2014-2016

Variants of improvement			Year			Total
A	B	C	2014	2015	2016	
a1	b1	c1	2.10	1.54	1.43	1.69
		c2	2.35	1.48	1.10	1.65
	b2	c1	2.15	1.78	1.06	1.66
		c2	2.72	2.05	1.51	2.09
a2	b1	c1	3.18	1.78	1.89	2.28
		c2	3.27	1.54	1.39	2.07
	b2	c1	2.60	1.60	1.48	1.89
		c2	2.78	2.51	1.83	2.37
a3	b1	c1	2.88	2.39	1.86	2.38
		c2	3.24	2.00	2.07	2.44
	b2	c1	2.93	2.18	2.16	2.42
		c2	4.05	2.36	2.76	3.06
Total			2.85	1.93	1.71	2.17

Table 2. Influence of paddocking factor on dry matter production
Blana Bucegi 2014 -2016

Organic fertilization	DM Production		Difference	The significance
	t/ha	%	t/ha	
a1 - Paddocking - 2 night	1.77	100	Control plot	
a2 - Paddocking - 4 night	2.15	121	0.38	**
a3 - Paddocking - 6 night	2.57	145	0.80	***
DL 5% = 0.15; DL 1% = 0.25; DL 0.1% = 0.47 t/ha				

Table 3. Influence of herbicide factor on dry matter production,
Blana Bucegi 2014 -2016

Herbicide	DM Production		Difference	The significance
	t/ha	%	t/ha	
No herbicide	2.08	100	C.p.	
Glyphosate 5L/ha	2.25	108	0.17	*
DL 5% = 0.14; DL 1% = 0.21; DL 0.1% = 0.35 t/ha				

Also, in case of herbicide and phosphorus fertilisation interaction of factors, significant differences were observed. Thus, the combination of factors b1c1(no herbicide - no fertiliser) were obtained 2.12 t / ha SU and the b2c2 (Glyphosate 5L/ha - 100 kg/ha P₂O₅) 2.51 t / ha (table 4).

Table 4. Interaction of factors herbicides and phosphorus fertilization,
Blana Bucegi 2014-2016

Herbicide	Fertilization	DM Production		Difference	The significance
		t/ha	%	t/ha	
b1 - no herbicide	c1 - no fertilization	2.12	100	C. p.	
	c2 - 100 kg/ha P ₂ O ₅	2.05	97	-0.07	
b2 - Glyphosate 5l/ha	c1 - no fertilization	1.99	94	-0.13	
	c2 - 100 kg/ha P ₂ O ₅	2.51	118	0.39	***
DL 5% = 0.19; DL 1% = 0.26; DL 0.1% = 0.36 t/ha					

The floristic composition

Improvement methods of nardetum have been profoundly changed the floristic composition in grassy carpet from experimental field.

The table 5 summarizes the average floristic composition for different variants of improvement by paddocking in comparison with mean of experiment. By paddocking applied with 1 cow/6 square meters during 2-6 night and herbicide spraying, are realise a decreasing up to 12% participation of unvaluable species *Nardus stricta* in grass cover. The species *Agrostis rupestris* and *Festuca nigrescens* have been replaced by more valuable sown species like *Phleum pratense*, *Festuca rubra* and *Festuca pratensis*.

In case of herbicide factor, we can notice a significant increasing (+20) of the percentage of participation in grass carpet structure of valuable sown species *Phleum pratense*. Also, the mean pastoral value of herbicide variants is with 12 points superior to the average of no herbicide variants.

When phosphorus fertilization is applied, decreasing of the percentage of participation of plants from other botanical families and increasing of participation of legumes in floristic composition were observed (table 6).

The fodder quality

Analysis of feed quality parameters from pasture (table 7) show that they are within the normal limits in subalpine conditions. Thus, at the contents in crude fiber, ADF (lignocellulose), NDF (fiber plant total) were recorded values quite high, while the content of lignin (ADL) which is a part of the cellular constituents of plants indigestible in the rumen of animals recorded values smaller than 7% (optimum).

The digestibility coefficients for organic matter have varied in small limits, being higher for paddocking with 1 cow /6 m² during 2 nights and smaller in case of 4 to 6 nights staying in paddock.

Organic matter digestibility was negatively affected by drought during the growing season, when rainfall was insufficient to ensure the water needs of plants.

Table 5. Residual effect of paddocking and overseeding on floristic composition ,
Blana Bucegi (2014-2016)

SPECIES	Forage quality index	A Factor PADDOKING			Mean of factors 000
		100	200	300	
Total GRASSES		78	81	74	78
a. overseeded species					
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	5	17	20	20	19
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	3	12	14	15	14
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	5	0	0	1	+
b. spontaneous species					
<i>Festuca nigrescens</i>	3	24	21	17	21
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	3	6	8	9	8
<i>Poa media</i>	1	5	4	2	4
<i>Deschampsia caespitosa</i>	0	2	6	4	4
<i>Agrostis rupestris</i>	1	4	4	2	3
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	0	3	2	0	2
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	4	1	2	3	2
<i>Phleum alpinum</i>	2	1	0	1	1
<i>Festuca ovina</i>	1	1	0	+	+
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	1	1	+	0	+
<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	0	1	+	0	+
Total LEGUMES		14	9	9	10
a. overseeded species					
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	4	12	8	7	9
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	4	2	1	1	1
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	4	+	+	+	+
OTHER FAMILIES		8	10	18	12
<i>Potentilla ternata</i>	0	6	5	5	5
<i>Polygonum bistorta</i>	1	0	1	7	3
<i>Ligusticum mutelina</i>	2	1	2	4	2
<i>Ranunculus montanus</i>	0	+	1	1	1
<i>Campanula napuligera</i>	0	1	1	+	1
<i>Campanula abietina</i>	0	+	+	0	+
<i>Alchemilla vulgaris</i>	2	+	+	1	+
<i>Hieracium aurantiacum</i>	0	0	0	+	+
<i>Geum montanum</i>	0	+	0	0	+
<i>Viola declinata</i>	0	+	+	+	+
Other species	0	+	+	+	+
Pastoral value	x	57	57	59	58

Table 6. Residual effect of herbicide and phosphorus fertilisation on floristic composition, Blana Bucegi, (2014-2016)

SPECIES	Forage quality index	B Factor HERBICIDE			Factor C PHOSPHORUS		
		010	020	Dif. + -	001	002	Dif. + -
Total GRASSES		75	80	+ 5	78	78	0
a. overseeded species							
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	5	9	29	+ 20	17	21	+ 4
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	3	16	10	- 6	15	12	- 3
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	5	1	+	- 1	1	1	0
b. spontaneous species							
<i>Festuca nigrescens</i>	3	27	13	- 14	21	20	- 1
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	3	5	11	+ 6	8	8	0
<i>Poa media</i>	1	3	4	+ 1	6	4	- 2
<i>Deschampsia caespitosa</i>	0	4	4	0	4	4	0
<i>Agrostis rupestris</i>	1	2	5	+ 3	5	3	- 2
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	0	3	+	- 3	2	1	- 1
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	4	+	3	+ 3	1	2	+ 1
<i>Phleum alpinum</i>	2	+	1	+ 1	+	1	+ 1
<i>Festuca ovina</i>	1	1	+	- 1	1	+	- 1
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	1	+	+	0	0	1	- 1
<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	0	1	+	- 1	1	+	- 1
Total LEGUMES		11	10	- 1	9	12	+ 3
a. overseeded species							
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	4	9	9	0	8	11	+ 3
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	4	2	1	- 1	1	1	0
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	4	+	+	0	+	+	0
OTHER FAMILIES		14	10	- 4	13	10	- 3
<i>Potentilla ternata</i>	0	5	5	0	5	4	- 1
<i>Polygonum bistorta</i>	1	4	1	- 3	4	1	- 3
<i>Ligusticum mutelina</i>	2	4	1	- 3	2	3	+ 1
<i>Ranunculus montanus</i>	0	+	1	+ 1	1	1	0
<i>Campanula napuligera</i>	0	1	1	0	1	1	0
<i>Campanula abietina</i>	0	+	+	0	+	+	0
<i>Alchemilla vulgaris</i>	2	+	1	+ 1	+	+	0
<i>Hieracium aurantiacum</i>	0	+	+	0	+	+	0
<i>Geum montanum</i>	0	+	+	0	+	+	0
<i>Viola declinata</i>	0	+	+	0	+	+	0
Other species	0	+	+	0	+	+	0
Pastoral value	x	51	63	+12	56	61	+5

Table 7. Results relating to chemical analyses of forage samples, Blana Bucegi 2014-2016

Variant	CP %	Ash %	Crude fiber %	ADF %	ADL %	NDF %	DSU %	DMO %
a1	8.63	6.38	38.19	40.74	5.33	65.59	49.70	46.35
a2	9.18	6.89	37.25	39.81	5.17	63.81	51.52	48.21
a3	8.68	6.54	37.80	40.15	5.08	64.71	51.08	47.39
b1	9.05	6.77	37.91	40.53	5.28	64.99	50.15	46.76
b2	8.61	6.43	37.59	39.93	5.10	64.41	51.38	47.86
c1	8.76	6.56	37.96	40.51	5.25	65.16	50.26	46.86
c2	8.90	6.64	37.54	39.95	5.13	64.25	51.27	47.77
Grand total	8.83	6.60	37.75	40.23	5.19	64.70	50.77	47.31

Agrochemical soil indices

Before placing the experience in 2008, soil samples were taken and analysed to determine the initial chemical composition of the soil. This year a new set of samples was taken. Results are interpreted taking into account the influence of each experimental factor on the soil agrochemical composition (table 8).

Agrochemical soil indices, after 8 years of experimentation, have had important changes as a result of the improvement measures applied. Analysing the modifications of pH indices and content of mobile aluminium, depending on the measures applied, illustrates the following:

paddock changes soil reaction depending on the used graduation - that meaning it records slight increase in paddocked variants (table 9).

Also, the degree of base saturation are positively influenced by paddocking, so that in the case of 6 nights standing in paddock to be higher with 25%.

Mobile aluminium content of the soil, which as it is known is toxic to plants, decreased from 6.8 mg / 100 g soil to 2.37 mg / 100 g soil where a paddocking intensity is a cow/6 m² for 6 nights, this reduction contributing to the improvement of plant nutrition.

Table 8. Agrochemical indices of soil, Blana Bucegi (2016)

Agrochemical indices	MU	2 nights					4 nights					6 nights				
		111	112	121	122	211	212	221	222	311	312	321	322			
pH	ind.	5	5	5	5.1	5	5	5	5	5.1	5.1	5.3				
Al _{mobile}	me/100g	3.172	3.099	3.203	2.350	3.068	3.162	3.141	3.141	2.86	2.808	2.631				
Ah	me/100g	19.8	18.3	18.4	17.1	19.2	23.3	18.8	19.6	18.3	19.5	19.2				
SB	me/100g	11.2	9.2	10.4	9.6	9.4	9.2	9.6	9.4	10.2	9.8	12.8				
V _{Ah}	%	36.1	33.5	36.1	35.9	32.8	28.3	33.8	32.4	35.8	33.4	38.5				
Hummus	%	15.96	16.08	15.12	14.4	16.92	16.8	16.2	15.48	14.76	16.56	14.76				
N Indice	ind.	5.761	5.386	5.458	5.169	5.539	4.754	5.475	5.015	5.284	5.531	6.996				
P-Al	ppm	24	20.5	17	19.2	22.8	20.5	21	26	18.5	22.8	19				
K-Al	ppm	104	104	130	128	142	146	128	146	116	132	144				

Table 9. Paddocking influence on agrochemical indices of soil, Blana Bucegi (2008-2016)

Agrochemical indices	MU	Initial		2 nights			4 nights			6 nights		
		2008	%	Ind.	Dif. ±	%	Ind.	Dif. ±	%	Ind.	Dif. ±	%
pH	ind.	4.6	100	5.03	+0.43	109	5	+0.4	109	5.15	+0.55	112
V _{Ah}	%	31	100	35.4	+4.4	114	31.38	+0.38	101	38.78	+7.78	125
Hummus	%	10	100	15.39	+5.39	154	15.57	+5.57	156	16.35	+6.35	164
P - Al	ppm	10.6	100	20.18	+9.58	190	22.5	+11.9	212	20.58	+9.98	194
K - Al	ppm	97	100	116.5	+19.5	120	130.5	+33.5	135	140.5	+43.5	145
Al ⁺⁺⁺	mg/100g	6.8	100	2.96	-3.84	44	3.13	-3.67	46	2.37	-4.43	35

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The improvement methods of *Nardus stricta* subalpine pastures have profoundly changed the floristic composition of the grassy carpet of the experimental field. Besides that sown species were installed well, it helps to expansion of spontaneous white clover;
- (2) Dry matter yield (DM) for the years 2014-2016 was 1.77 t/ha in version 2 nights of paddocking and reach 2.57 t/ha in variant with paddocking a cow/6 nights / 6 square meters, an increase by 45%;
- (3) The quality of forages from subalpine improved grasslands, characterised by their specific conditions, is in normal limits. Increase of intensity of paddocking influence positively the forage dry matter digestibility;
- (4) Agrochemical soil indices have changed as a result of the improvement measures applied, contributing to the improvement of plant nutrition;
- (5) By repeating, from 4-6 t 4-6 years period, of paddocking fertilization method of subalpine pastures, where complex improved measures have been applied is achieved their influence reactivation with beneficial effects on the quantity and quality of feed and animal products and thus economic efficiency of utilisation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bărbulescu C., Gh. Motcă, 1983, *Pășunile munților înalți*, Ed. Ceres București
- [2] Bărbulescu C., P. Burcea, Al. Ștefănescu, Gh. Motcă, Gh. Marinică, 1975, *Cercetări privind valorificarea superioară a pajiștilor alpine din Masivul Iezer-Păpușa*, Lucrări științifice ale SCCP Măgurele – Brașov, vol.I, 13-24
- Rotar, I., Carlier, L., 2005, *Cultura Pajiștilor*. Editura Risoprint, Cluj-Napoca, 321p.
- [3] Blaj V. A., Marușca T., Mocanu V. Haș E.C., Constantinescu S.C., 2012, *The combined effect of paddocking, phosphorus fertilisation and oversowing on degraded Nardus stricta L. pastures*, Journal of Mountain Agriculture on the Balkans, vol. 15, nr.3, pp.563-575, Bulgaria, ISSN 1311 - 0489
- [4] Laza Gh., 1980, *Cercetări privind îmbunătățirea pajiștilor de Nardus stricta din Munții Bihorului*, Lucrări științifice ale Stațiunii Centrale de Cercetări pentru Cultura Pajiștilor Măgurele – Brașov, vol.VI, 157-164

- [5] Marușca T., J. Frame, 2003, *Pasture improvement strategies in the Carpathians package with dairy cows*, EGF, Bulgaria, Optimal Forage Systems for Animal Production and the Environment, Grassland Science in Europe, vol.8, 219-221
- [6] Pușcaru D., Pușcaru-Soroceanu E., Paucă A., Șerbănescu I., Beldie Al., Ștefureac Tr., Cernescu N., Saghin N., Crețu V., Lupan L., Tașcenco V., 1956, *Pășunile alpine din Munții Bucegi*, Ed. Academiei Republicii Populare Române
- [7] Samoilă Z. et al., 1963, *Rezultate experimentale privind transformarea asociației de Nardus stricta prin măsuri agrotehnice de suprafață și radicale*, Studii și cercetări științifice, Baza Academiei Timișoara, tom XV, nr. 3.

RESEARCH OF WATER LOGGING AND COMPACTION CONTROL OF THE SOILS FROM THE BIHOR COUNTY

Radu BREJEA^{1,2}, Iuliu COLIBAȘ¹, Maria COLIBAȘ¹, Cornel DOMUȚA^{1,2},
Maria ȘANDOR¹, Nicu Cornel SABĂU¹, Ioana BORZA¹,
Mariana BEI¹, Ana PEREȘ¹, Manuel GÎTEA¹, Nandor KOTELES¹,
Andrei NISTOR¹, Nicolae CENUȘA¹

Abstract. *The paper is based on the research carried out in Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea starting with 1967. The research were carried out in the research field from Petid, Buntesti, Cefa, Avram Iancu, Sanmartin, Bihor county. Research on compacted soils in the North-West on Romania, aimed to identify solutions for preventing and control the soil compaction, through the application of best and effective measures to increase and maintain soil fertility parameters. Secondary compaction of the soil has negative effects on physical and microbiological properties of the soil, and also on the nutrition conditions for plants. These negative effects can be tackled through adequate long-term measures and in a sustainable development context.*

Key words: secondary compaction, deep loosening, drainage, melioration crop rotation, organic fertilization.

1. Introduction

In the Bihor county, humidity excess is the limiting factor of soil fertility, the most widespread of which is associated frequent with argillic alteration and soil compaction (the primary one from Bt horizons of argilluvisoil and secondary - layer and that immediately lower layer), acid or salinized. Thus, in Bihor county is required deep chiselling on 94 thousand hectares, subsoiling works on 176 thousand hectares, acid soil amendment on 165 thousand hectares of the alkali on 9,000 ha, modeling the ridges on 73 thousand hectares, antierosion soil work on 43 thousand hectares, plowing on the drainage direction on 55 thousand hectares, drainage on 168 thousand hectares, leveling operating on 216 thousand hectares, unsystematic ditches and gullies on 213 thousand hectares. [1, 2, 3, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17].

Research in knowledge and improving heavy soils affected by humidity excess began in 1967, by pedoameliorative characterization and organization of field research in the specific conditions of these soils: Depression Holod on the second

¹ University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 Gen. Magheru St., 410048 Oradea Romania. Corresponding author: email: rbreja@yahoo.com

² Academy of Romania Scientists, Splaiul Independenței 54, 050094, Bucharest, Romania

terrace of Crisul Negru at Petid (1967) in the Crisurilor Piedmont Plain at Sanmartin (1968); Besiusului Depression at Buntesti (1974); High Plain of Crişul Repede from Oradea (1981); in the Cefa (1982) and the low plain of Crisul Negru at Avram Iancu (1983) [4,5,6,7,8].

2. Material and method

Climatic research field is characterized by annual average temperature of 9.6°C at Buntesti, 10.1°C at Petid, 10.5°C at Oradea and 10.8°C in Cefa and Avram Iancu. In the wetlands in Depresiunea Beiuşului and Holod at Buntesti and Petid, annual rainfall exceeded 700 mm, real evapotranspiration is relatively low (575-587 mm) and humidity excess was 136-120 mm.

The main characteristics of soils revealed a number physical, chemical and hydro indices that were limiting their fertility, differentiated on research fields (Table 1).

Table 1.

The main properties of the soil in the research fields

Location and soil type	Horizon	Depth cm	Clay <0,002%	BD g/cm ³	TP %	FC %	K mm/h	pH H ₂ O	Al mobil mg/100 g soil	Humus %	P K	
											mobile ppm	ppm
ORADEA	1.	0-24	31.5	1.33	51	23.0	21.0	5.5	3.7	2.32	22.0	83.0
	2.	24-34	31.6	1.38	49	23.2	9.0	5.6	2.3	2.28	23.0	102.0
	3.	34-54	40.0	1.44	47	23.7	6.0	6.2	0.5	1.91	6.0	112.0
	4.	54-78	39.3	1.55	43	24.6	1.0	6.3	0.8	1.93	6.0	118.0
	5.	78-95	39.2	1.62	40	24.6	0.5	6.6	0.3	-	-	-
	6.	95-145	37.6	1.66	39	24.5	0.1	6.5	0.6	-	-	-
SÎNMARTIN	1.	0-22	24.7	1.24	53	23.0	5.5	5.1	1.0	2.80	12.6	59.8
	2.	22-32	23.7	1.52	43	23.0	1.9	5.2	1.4	1.27	11.8	60.0
	3.	32-44	30.0	1.54	43	23.0	1.3	5.2	5.5	1.50	7.8	73.0
	4.	44-90	43.3	1.63	40	24.0	0.2	5.4	2.4	-	7.0	63.9
	5	90-100	40.2	1.65	39	23.0	0.2	5.9	1.2	-	-	-
PETID	1.	0-20	19.8	1.34	50	24.5	6.4	6.1	2.3	1.94	13.9	66.4
	2.	20-39	26.4	1.48	47	24.2	2.6	5.6	2.8	1.34	9.6	66.4
	3.	32-49	39.9	1.45	46	25.4	1.7	5.4	3.4	0.99	4.5	116.2
	4.	49-90	48.7	1.50	44	26.1	0.9	5.7	2.6	0.94	-	-
	5.	90-110	44.7	1.58	41	23.0	0.4	6.3	2.0	0.87	-	-
BUNTEȘTI	1.	0-21	25.7	1.33	51	22.8	6.3	4.8	30.4	2.0	12.2	41.5
	2.	21-43	26.7	1.45	46	22.9	2.5	5.1	38.3	1.10	4.0	20.7
	3.	43-55	35.5	1.55	43	23.4	1.1	5.3	57.1	0.40	3.5	24.9
	4.	55-92	36.7	1.56	42	23.4	0.6	5.5	39.3	-	-	-
	5.	92-109	33.7	1.56	42	23.3	0.5	5.6	19.7	-	-	-
CEFA	1.	0-26	40.3	1.35	50	27.7	6.1	7.7	5.1*)	2.60	7.8	74.7
	2.	26-45	41.1	1.46	46	27.0	4.5	8.0	10.8	0.90	3.5	99.6
	3.	45-58	43.1	1.57	42	28.3	1.7	8.6	10.0	1.00	3.0	83.0
	4.	58-81	44.4	1.60	41	27.1	0.6	8.9	12.1	0.90	3.5	99.6
	5.	81-103	41.0	1.57	42	26.0	0.7	9.1	13.7	-	-	-

BD = bulk density; TP= total porosity; FC= field capacity; k= hydraulic conductivity

P= phosphorus, K= potassium

Table 2.

Influence of modeling land ridges on eliminating excess water and increasing production on luvisoil albic amfigleic from Petid - Bihor.

Variant	Winter wheat		Maize		Water volume evacuated in cold season	
	q/ha	%	q/ha	%	m ³ /ha	% from rainfall
Ploughland	-	100	-	100	-	-
Modeling – 16 m distance	1.5	108	0.9	103	556	26.3
Modeling – 24 m distance	2.5	113	6.8	123	479	23.6
Modeling – 32 m distance	0.2	101	3.9	113	468	22.2

According to data obtained and presented in Table 2, Land modeling in ridge with the width of 24 m of the soil and a length of 200-300 m, proved to be an efficient rainwater humidity excess combat, practicable under current conditions.

Results obtained in the research field from Buntesti

The research was conducted on luvisols, under a water balance surplus exceeding 130 mm.

The measures investigated for the removal of excess water were different drain types: ceramic drains 15 and located 25 m away and 0.8 m in depth, drains of stone at 10 and 20 m distance plus perpendicular scarification with the drain lines for soil permeability and facilitating the rain water to drain plus scarification. The soil was amended with 10 t / ha of CaCO₃ and annual it was applied N₁₃₀P₉₀ kg / ha in wheat-clover -maize-oil crop rotation, each drainage variant being subdivided for the four crops.

The water volume drained through the drainage system in relation to climatic conditions. During 13 years of research, the results of the discharged water volume, allow ordering variants of removing excess moisture so: ceramic drainage on 10 m distance with the highest annual leakage (2.902 m³/ ha or 46% precipitation), followed by shaping the ridge (1.428 m³/ha), shaping the ridges plus scarification (1.173 m³/ha), ceramic drainage 15 m (1.220 m³/ha), 25 m (1.038 m³/ ha) and rock drainage at 10 and 20 m (387 respectively 689 m³/ ha). The volumes of water removed in the highest amount, were recorded in the months of December to March. Water leakage through drains recorded the highest frequency in February (13 years), March and April (12) and January and May (in 10 years of 13).

Over the research period, the maximum leakage of water in 24 hours was of 39 m³/ha at the drainage system with ceramic tubes at 10 m distance. The variations are preserved and spills within 24 hours maximum sense of variation around the research period.

The chemical content of the water drained through the drains and gullies, averages on 13 years of researched elements, Highlight the discharge of large amounts of nitrogen that reach up to 26.8 kg N / ha / year version with intensity the maximum drainage. The amounts of phosphorus are low (0.1-0.6 kg / ha), also the potassium in the absence of the application of fertilizers potassium. In Table 3 it can be seen that a stone drain with a diameter of 20 meters, evacuates a small amounts of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium (Table 3).

Table 3.

Amounts of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium evacuated annually on drains, Buntesti, Bihor

Variant		N	P	K
		kg/ha/year		
1.	Ceramic drain, d=10m+scarification	26.8	0.6	0.6
2.	Ceramic drain, d=15m+scarification	16.2	0.3	0.5
3.	Ceramic drain, d=25m+scarification	14.5	0.3	0.4
4.	Stone drain, d=10 m+scarification	7.8	0.2	0.3
5.	Stone drain, d=20 m+scarification	4.5	0.1	0.2
6.	Modeling, l=20m; L=200m	18.1	0.3	0.8
7.	Modeling+scarification	13.2	0.4	1.0

Drainage and scarification are as bulk density decreased to 4-5%, while the air porosity maintained at medium values in all variants.

Penetration resistance decreases by 24-29% between 20-60 cm and hydraulic conductivity values go from medium to high levels of soil layer at 20-40 cm and at low values to medium values between 40- 60 cm depth.

Research results reveal significant improvements in their application under the influence of CaCO₃, scarification, eliminating the water excess, annual fertilization crop rotation. Thus, highly acid soil reaction initial field pass in the acid or weak acid. The ratio of nitrate nitrogen to the ammonia improves very significantly in favor of nitric and has been a significant improvement in the supply of phosphorus and even potassium (without the application of fertilizer

with potassium), following the application of annual fertilizer with phosphorus (P90 kg/ha) in the soil and creating favorable conditions to mobilization of phosphorus and potassium in the soil.

The agrophytotechnical measures applied to remove excessive moisture, raising deep prick, shaping the land in ridges with and without scarification, and other, influenced positively the soil yielding.

The average yield increases that have been achieved over the years of research shows that the measures taken have had a positive effect on productivity. Thus, for winter wheat were obtained increases on the average 13 years old, range from 3.8 to 7.0 q / ha (20-37%) compared to the normal plowing, at maize - between 5.4 to 11.5 q / ha (20-43%), at clover from 1.0-1.4 t / ha hay (14-19%) and at oil flax between 100-160 kg / ha (20-34%) (Table 4).

Table 4.

The influence of drainage, modeling and scarification on yield gain in winter wheat, clover and oil flax at Buntesi – Bihor

Variant	Yield gain							
	Winter Wheat		Maize		Clover		Oil flax	
	q/ha	%	q/ha	%	t/ha	%	Kg/ha	%
Control, ploughland	-	100	-	100	-	100	-	100
Ceramic drain, d=10m+scarification	6.7	135	7.2	127	1.4	119	124	126
Ceramic drain, d=15m+scarification	6.8	136	8.6	132	1.3	118	150	132
Ceramic drain, d=25m+scarification	5.0	126	5.4	120	1.2	117	96	120
Stone drain, d=10m+scarification	7.0	137	9.4	135	1.2	117	162	134
Stone drain, d=20m+scarification	6.4	134	7.8	129	1.4	119	109	123
Modeling, l=20m; L=200m	3.0	120	8.5	132	1.3	118	16	134
Modelling+scarification	4.4	123	11.5	143	1.0	114	126	127

The biggest production increases were generally made on ceramic drainage at 15 m distance, stone drainage at 10 m.

Results obtained in the research field from Cefa

The soil from research field is gluey humic soil.

In research field from Cefa, the period was characterized by dry years, the volumes of water discharged during the excess periods ranged from 67-363 m³/ ha. Throughout the research period there were no puddles of water on the ground surface (Table 5).

For the improvement of soil characteristics was performed and soil scarification has helped to increase the drained water volume by 37% - 97% depending on the height of the filtering material, scarification has the best effect when filter material with lower height.

The maximum discharge volume in 24 hours in different types of drainage ranged from 26 respectively 108.9 m³.

The agricultural output has risen significantly between 6.3 (15%) and 11.3 q / ha wheat (26%), obtained only in the case of scarification work on drainage 30m away, both at the small and at the high filter. It also notes the good influence of high filter to small filter.

Table 5.

Influence of the drainage distance and of the filter on winter wheat yield and evacuated water in the conditions from Cefa - Bihor

Variant	Winter wheat production			Evacuated water volume	
	q/ha	%	dif	m ³ /ha	%
Control, ploughland	43.0	100	-	-	-
Drain, d=30m F small	45.7	106	2.7	67	100
Drain, d=30m F small+sc	49.3	115	6.3	132	197
Drain, d=30m Fî	46.4	108	3.4	165	100
Drain, d=30m Fî +sc	54.3	126	11.3	363	137

F small = small filter (5-10 cm); Fî = high filter (25-30 cm); sc = scarification

Results obtained in the research field from Avram Iancu

The soil from research field Avram Iancu are gluey humic soil.

In terms of Avram Iancu, the discharged water volume by drains in excess periods were between 215 and 615 m³ / ha. Soil scarification applied on the drain, influenced the increase by 49-149% of the volumes of water discharged by drains. The maximum discharged water volume recorded in 24 hours ranged from 16.2 to 61.6 m³ / ha. The mole drainage applied to corrugated drainage tube without filter, increased the drained water volume by 74% and the scarification with 95%. It can be said that the achieved production in maize ranged from 0.9 q / ha with 30 m

unfiltered drain and without scarification and 11.7 q / ha (31%) than normal plowing in case of 30m when completed with filter and high permeability soil prick (4.6.). Scarifying increases the production by 15% on drain without filter, 17% on lower filter and 20% on higher filter drainage (Table 6).

The economic efficiency analysis reveals that the high filter drainage at 30 m distance is the most efficient, followed by the low filter drainage and scarification at 30 m, and the drainage without filter at 30 m is less efficient.

The amortization period of the soil improvement by drainage, highlights the fact that in marshy clay, the drainage without scarification of soil permeability is not justified. The effect period of the plastic corrugated tube drainage is estimated at 30 years, or in drainage without scarification this period is longer; so without scarifying drainage, this system is not profitable.

In terms of energy efficiency, the highest values were registered between 26-35at the drainage with scarification.

Table 6

The influence of the drainage on maize yield gain and evacuated water in the conditions from Avram Iancu, Bihor

Variant	Yield gain		Evacuated water volume	
	q/ha	%	m ² /ha	%
Control, ploughland	-	100	-	-
Drain, d=30m	0.9	102	215	100
Drain, d=30m +f scarif	6.5	117	361	168
Drain, d=30m F small	2.4	106	239	100
Drain, d=30m F small+scar	8.9	123	570	249
Drain, d=30m Fî	4.3	111	413	100
Drain, d=30m Fî+scar	11.7	131	615	149

F small = small filter (5-10 cm); Fî = high filter (25-30 cm); sc = scarification

The results achieved in amelioration of the limitative factors of the heavy soil fertility, highlight the need for detailed knowledge of soil conditions and climate.

Conclusion

The research on compacted soils in the Bihor county, aimed to identify solutions for preventing and control the soil compaction, through the application of best and effective measures to increase and maintain soil fertility parameters. The researches were conducted in several research fields from the Bihor county, as

follows: Petid, Buntesti, Cefa , Avram Iancu. The improvement of soil water balance was studied, too; the different types of drains and distance of placement were studied. The drains were placement using the high or short filter in association with scarification.

According to the research, to increase the productivity of the soil from Depresiunea Holod, is needed to design the land ridge width with 24 m and length of 200-300m, which is the most suitable measure to remove excess moisture. The modeling at 24 m distance determined yield gains of 2,5 q/ha in winter wheat and 6,8 q/ha in maize.

Regarding the research field from Buntesti, the agrophytotechnical measures applied to remove excessive moisture, deep ripping raising, fertilizers application in optimal amounts, had a significant influence, resulting in increases of agricultural production. The biggest quantities of nitrogen and potassium evacuated in the average on the year were registered in the variant with ceramic drains at 10 m distance and scarification

The research from Cefa and Avram Iancu in order to remove excessive moisture, to permeabilize the soil by draining, scarification, gave very good results in terms of agricultural productivity. Both in Cefa and Avram Iancu the biggest yield gain in winter wheat and maize, and the biggest water quantity evacuated were registered in the variant with drains placed at 30 m distance, high filter and scarification.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Brejea R., 2010, *Știința solului – îndrumător de lucrări practice*. Editura Universității din Oradea.
- [2]. Brejea R., Domuța C., 2011, *Practicum de pedologie*. Editura Universității din Oradea.
- [3]. Brejea R., 2011, *Practicum de tehnologii de protecție a solurilor*. Editura Universității din Oradea.
- [4]. Brejea R., 2014, *Tehnologii de Protecție a Solurilor*. Editura Universității din Oradea.
- [5]. Colibaș I., Colibaș M., *Rezultate ale cercetărilor privind ameliorarea prin măsuri agro, pedo și hidroameliorative a solurilor cu exces temporar de umiditate din depresiunea Beiușului-Bihor*. Lucr. Conf. Naț. pt. Știința Solului, Brăila, vol. XXI –A, pp. 102 – 109, (1983)

- [6]. Colibaș I., Colibaș M., Șandor M., *Cercetări privind cunoașterea și ameliorarea unor factori negativi ai fertilității solurilor grale și tasate, afectate de exces de umiditate, din Câmpia Crișurilor și depresiunile Holod și Beiuș*, în volumul „Contribuții ale cercetării științifice la dezvoltarea agriculturii din zona centrală a Câmpiei de vest, 25 de ani de activitate a S.C.A.Z. Oradea”, București, Red. de propagandă tehnică agricolă, pp. 445 – 496, (1988)
- [7]. Colibaș I., et al, *Efectul lucrărilor de scarificare în asocieri cu culturi ameliorative în asolament în condițiile solurilor grele tasate din Câmpia piemontană a Crișurilor*. Rev. Producția vegetală – cereale și plante tehnice, nr. 2., (1990)
- [8]. Domuța C., - *Agrotehnica diferențiată*, Editura Universității din Oradea, 7, (2006)
- [9]. Domuța C., Brejea R., - *Monitoringul mediului*, Ed. Universității din Oradea, (2010)
- [10]. Domuța C. (coord.) și colab., - *50 de ani de cercetări agricole în Oradea*, Ed. Univeristății din Oradea, (2012)
- [11]. Păcurar I., Buta M. - *Pedologie și bonitatea terenurilor agricole*, Ed. Risoprint Cluj Napoca, (2010)
- [12]. Rusu T., și colab. - *Metode de cercetare ale solului și plantei*, Ed. Risoprint Cluj Napoca, (2009)
- [13]. Șandor M., *Economical and energetically efficiency of the drainage and meliorations measures on the humic gly soil from research field-Cefa, Bihor*. Natural Ressources and Sustainable Development, 23-24 aprilie pag. 46 (2004)
- [14]. Șandor M., *The influence of the king exploitation on the vegetation from canals and of the drainage parameters from the research field Cefa, Bihor*. University of Oradea, Faculty of Enviromment Protection- University of Debrecen. Natural Ressources and Sustainable Development, 23-24 aprilie pag 46, (2004)
- [15]. Șandor M., *Combaterea excesului de umiditate în Câmpia Crișurilor*. Editura Universității din Oradea.(2007)
- [16]. Șandor M., *Ameliorarea lăcoviștilor din Câmpia Crișurilor*. Editura Universității din Oradea (2007)
- [17]. Șandor M., *Ameliorarea solurilor cu exces de umiditate din Câmpia Crișurilor*. Editura Universității din Oradea (2007)

RESEARCH FOR THE DETERMINATION OF THE OPTIMUM WATER CONSUMPTION OF THE MAIN CROPS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF THE IRRIGATION SCHEDULING IN DIFFERENT ROMANIA'S ZONES

Cornel DOMUȚA^{1,2}, Nicolae GRUMEZA¹, Cristian DOMUȚA¹,
Radu BREJEA^{1,2}, Ioana BORZA¹, Ana PEREȘ¹, Manuel GÎTEA¹,
Nandor KOTELES¹, Nicolae CENUȘA¹, Andrei NISTOR¹

Abstract. *Research programme “Exploitation of the Irrigation and Drainage” of the Research Institute for irrigation and Drainage Băneasa – Giurgiu had research fields (30) in the all the areas of Romania. Crop coefficients “Kc” are used in the irrigation scheduling and it is obtained like report between water consumption and pan evaporation determined daily at 8⁰⁰ o'clock. In the 12 location (Oradea, Suceava, Podu Iloaiei, Tecuci, Braila, Valul lui Traian, Dor Marunt, Baneasa – Giurgiu, Caracal, Siminic, Malu Mare and Maglovit) were placed the research fields and the research results obtained in winter wheat, maize, sunflower, soybean, sugar beet, and alfalfa are presented. The daily water consumption of crops differs depending on the month and the locality. Whereas Romania, in all the areas of interest for irrigation, has an impressive database for irrigation scheduling using the pan class A, is recommended to improve the current situation by using the variable depths for irrigation, depending on the growth rate of the root canal system and not of a fixed depths as at present.*

Keywords: crop coefficient, irrigation scheduling, research field, water consumption, evaporation

1. Introduction

Irrigation scheduling is of all the measures which have as main objective the provision of the moment the application of irrigating and compilation and transmission of documents and the necessary data for the information of the beneficiaries [4, 14].

The problem to the establishment of the correct application of the moment of irrigation applied has constituted an important preoccupation of specialists in the field. This fact depends on to the greatest extent possible to obtain the expected yields and the prevention of negative phenomena in the evolution of the soil and groundwater [10, 15, 16].

¹ University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, 26 Gen. Magheru Gh., 410048 Oradea Romania, Corresponding author: email: domuta_cornel@yahoo.com

² Academy of Romania Scientists, Splaiul Independenței 54, 050094, Bucharest, Romania

The methods and processes used over time in the irrigation scheduling have been designed specifically for this purpose or were taken from other areas, some adaptations. Methods for the irrigation scheduling shall take into account the relations in the soil-system-water-plant-climate [5-9]. When selecting the method for the irrigation scheduling the view is and the type of arrangement used in the irrigation, the mode of application of the irrigation (in Romania is used irrigation by rotation), the structure of crops, the characteristics of the organizational and technical (the size of the system and of the sectors of irrigation, the dimensions of the soil of the occupied with the crops, the beneficiaries etc.) considerations of efficiency and last but not least, economy ones [17, 18, 19].

Grumeza (1989) classifies the methods of irrigation scheduling into the following groups: the method of extrapolation of data on the reserve of water from the plots of the control; methods based on the relationship between the water consumption of plants and reference evaporation of reference determined using evaporimeter, climate formula, lysimeters etc. and methods based on the use of physiological indicators.

Domuța C. (2000) considers that the methods of irrigation scheduling can be grouped as follows:

- a) direct methods - based on the control of soil moisture by: the gravimetric method; the tensiometer method; neutron method; and methods based on the physiological indicators of plants;
- b) indirect methods - based on the connection between the water consumption of the reference evapotranspiration (ET_o). These method involves the use of the coefficients K_c for processing ET_o in the optimal use of water. These coefficients have settled in Romania after a specific methodology carried out by Grumeza (1987, 2005).

2. Material and methods

In the international scientific literature 'K_c' (crop coefficient) represents the coefficient of culture medium used for the conversion of reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) in the optimal water consumption of the crop. As a result, the calculation formula of it, is the following:

$$K_c = \frac{\text{Optimum daily consumption}}{\text{Daily reference evapotranspiration}}$$

In the immediate vicinity of each research field for soil water balance into the soil operates a station for irrigation scheduling. Here is determined the daily evaporated water with evaporimeter Bac pan class A. The existence of a complex, meteorological machine (meteorological stations, automatic transmission, etc.) which allows air temperature determination, the sun brilliance duration, air

humidity, wind speed, creates the premises for determination of other types of evapotranspiration reference (Thornthwaite Penman, etc.) in addition to the evaporation. Through the reporting of data for optimal daily water consumption, calculated on months or on phenophase at values of the evapotranspiration reference are obtained Kc values, [1, 3].

Fig. 1. The long term trial for establishing the optimum water consumption,
Oradea 1976-2015

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. The irrigation influence on the water consumption of winter wheat

The use of irrigating while maintaining the reserve of water on the depth of wetting between the easily available water content and field capacity determines a substantial improvement of the daily water consumption of water of winter wheat. Thus, in the conditions of the area moderately sub-humid of the Crisurilor Plain in the period 1976-2014 the average values of the water consumption have been higher than in conditions of non-irrigated with 19% - 56 %, noticing that the maximum difference was recorded in the last month of vegetation, plant leaves while the work in an extended period of time.

Table 1.

The daily average water consumption ($\text{m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$) of winter wheat in different areas of Romania

Zone	Location	Variant	Month			
			April	May	June	July
Crisurilor Plain	Oradea (1976-2014)	Unirrigated	26	33	17	
		Irrigated	31	45	20	
North Moldavia	Podu Iloaiei	Irrigated	27	43	-	
Baraganului Plain	Braila	Irrigated	23	42	-	
Dobrogea	Valu lui Traian	Irrigated	30	48	-	
Baraganului Plain	Marculesti	Irrigated	28	44	-	
Burnasului Plain	Băneasa Giurgiu	Irrigated	38	41	-	
Olteniei Plain	Caracal	Irrigated	29	41	-	
Central Part of Transilvania	Cluj Napoca	Irrigated	-	-	-	

In the month of April the largest daily water consumption of winter wheat were registered in Burnasului Plain, at Baneasa Giurgiu, $38 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$ and the smallest in Braila in Baragan Plain, $23 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$. During the month of May the largest water consumption has been registered at the Valu Traian in Dobrogea and the lowest daily consumption has been registered in Podu Iloaiei. In the June, the highest value optimal consumption of water has been registered in Oradea, and the lowest in Podul Iloaiei; in the localities of Oradea, Braila, Baneasa-Giurgiu and Caracal were recorded the maximum values of the daily consumption of water of winter wheat.

3.2. The irrigation influence on the maize water consumption

Ensuring the maintenance of the reserve of water between the easily available water content and the field ability on the watering depth using the irrigation is carried out conditions for the increase in value of the daily consumption, the highest relative difference (77 %) was recorded in the month of August.

The values for the optimum daily water content of maize differ. In the April the largest optimum water consumption of the maize has been registered at the Băneasa-Giurgiu ($22 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in May in Oradea ($30 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in June in Marculesti ($43 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in July in Marculesti and Oradea ($61 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in August in Marculesti ($54 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$) and in September in Marculesti and Braila ($28 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$)

Table 2.

The daily water consumption ($m^3/ha/day$) of maize in different areas of Romania

Zone	Location	Variant	Month					
			April	May	June	July	August	September
Crisurilor Plain	Oradea (1976-2014)	Unirrigated	15	26	36	40	27	16
		Irrigated	18	30	42	61	48	27
North Moldavia	Podu Iloaiei	Irrigated	15	25	39	51	38	19
Baraganului Plain	Braila	Irrigated	16	19	41	58	51	28
Dobrogea	Valu lui Traian	Irrigated	13	21	34	58	49	21
Baraganului Plain	Marculesti	Irrigated	14	22	40	61	54	28
Burnasului Plain	Băneasa Giurgiu	Irrigated	22	28	43	58	43	27
Olteniei Plain	Caracal	Irrigated	18	26	39	59	42	24
Central Part of Transilvania	Cluj Napoca	Irrigated	17	26	34	39	31	22

3.3. The irrigation influence on the sunflower water consumption

Daily values of the daily water consumption grow in conditions of irrigation use. In the April the highest value daily water consumption in sunflower has been registered at Băneasa-Giurgiu ($23 m^3/ha/day$), in May at Caracal ($35 m^3/ha/day$), in June at Marculesti ($61 m^3/ha/day$), in July at Marculesti ($66 m^3/ha/day$), and in August at Baneasa - Giurgiu ($48 m^3/ha/day$).

Table 3.

The daily average water consumption ($m^3/ha/day$) of sunflower in different areas of Romania

Zone	Location	Variant	Month				
			IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
Crisurilor Plain	Oradea (1976-2014)	Unirrigated	9	27	40	38	20
		Irrigated	21	31	54	60	38
North Moldavia	Podu Iloaiei	Irrigated	20	27	44	54	38
Baraganului Plain	Braila	Irrigated	14	26	50	58	32
Dobrogea	Valu lui Traian	Irrigated	17	24	54	62	30
Baraganului Plain	Marculesti	Irrigated	15	24	61	66	29
Burnasului Plain	Băneasa Giurgiu	Irrigated	23	32	53	52	48
Olteniei Plain	Caracal	Irrigated	16	35	56	58	26

3.4. The irrigation influence on the sugar beet water consumption

The ensurance of soil water reserve between easily available water content and field capacity, the water accessibility and the conditions of microclimate. It determine the increase of the daily consumption of water in sugar beet.

Monthly, the highest values of the optimal consumption of sugar beet were recorded in Oradea in April ($24 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), and May ($30 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), at Valu Traian in June ($53 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), at Marculesti in July ($62 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), at Baneasa Giurgiu in august ($51 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$) and in Oradea in September ($30 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$).

Table 4.

The daily water consumption ($\text{m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$) of sugar beet in different areas of Romania

Zone	Location	Variant	Month					
			IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
Crisurilor Plain	Oradea (1976-2014)	Unirrigated	20	28	37	36	25	18
		Irrigated	24	33	49	57	47	30
North Moldavia	Podu Iloaiei	Irrigated	19	25	45	51	38	29
Baraganului Plain	Braila	Irrigated	15	23	46	57	49	29
Dobrogea	Valu lui Traian	Irrigated	16	24	53	56	47	29
Baraganului Plain	Marculesti	Irrigated	14	25	48	62	50	29
Burnasului Plain	Băneasa Giurgiu	Irrigated	20	28	49	56	51	25
Olteniei Plain	Caracal	Irrigated	18	28	49	55	44	28
Central Part of Transilvania	Cluj-Napoca	Irrigated	17	25	35	43	31	19

3.5. The irrigation influence on potato water consumption

Monthly, the highest values of the optimal consumption of water at potato were registered as follows: in April at Baneasa-Giurgiu ($20 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in May in Oradea ($31 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in June at Valu Traian ($54 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in July at Baneasa Giurgiu (56%), in August at Baneasa Giurgiu (37%). In September the potato has been at vegetation only at Podu Iloaiei ($17 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$) and Cluj-Napoca ($22 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$).

Table 5.

The daily average water consumption (m³/ha/day) in potato in different areas of Romania

Zone	Location	Variant	Month					
			IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
Crisurilor Plain	Oradea (1976-2014)	Nonirrigated	18	27	33	34	22	-
		Irrigated	19	31	50	51	35	-
North Moldavia	Podu Iloaiei	Irrigated	19	27	48	43	30	17
Baraganului Plain	Braila	Irrigated	18	25	48	47	33	-
Dobrogea	Valu lui Traian	Irrigated	16	29	54	54	29	-
Baraganului Plain	Marculesti	Irrigated	12	24	49	48	32	-
Burnasului Plain	Băneasa Giurgiu	Irrigated	20	27	48	56	37	-
Olteniei Plain	Caracal	Irrigated	18	29	43	43	23	-
Central Part of Transilvania	Cluj-Napoca	Irrigated	18	26	39	45	32	22

3.6. The influence of irrigation on water consumption in maize for silo

In July, the highest value of the optimum daily water consumption for double maize for silo has been registered at Baneasa Giurgiu, 40 m³/ha/day in August the highest value has been registered in Oradea 44 m³/ha/day, and in September the highest value has been registered at the Valu Traian, 54 m³/ha/day.

Table 6.

The daily water consumption (m³/ha/day) on double maize for silo in different areas of Romania

Zone	Location	Variant	Month		
			VII	VIII	IX
Crisurilor Plain	Oradea (1976-2014)	Nonirrigated	16	21	18
		Irrigated	39	44	33
North Moldavia	Podu Iloaiei	Irrigated	26	32	26
Baraganului Plain	Braila	Irrigated	32	37	30
Dobrogea	Valu lui Traian	Irrigated	23	33	54
Baraganului Plain	Marculesti	Irrigated	26	40	32
Burnasului Plain	Băneasa Giurgiu	Irrigated	40	42	36
Olteniei Plain	Caracal	Irrigated	27	39	28
Central Part of Transilvania	Cluj-Napoca	Irrigated	33	33	29

Conclusions

The paper is based on the research field for soil water balance study placed by Research Institute for Irrigation and Drainage Băneasa-Giurgiu, in the Crișurilor Plain (Oradea), North Moldavia (Podu Iloaiei), Dobrogea (Valu lui Traian), Bărăgan (Brăila, Mărculești), Burnășului Plain (Băneasa-Giurgiu), Olteniei Plain (Caracal) and Central Part of Transilvania.

In June, the highest value of winter wheat water consumption has been registered in Oradea, and the lowest in Podul Iloaiei. The values for the optimum daily water content for maize differ: in April at the Băneasa-Giurgiu ($22 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in May in Oradea ($30 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in June in Marculesti ($43 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in July in Marculesti and Oradea ($61 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), during the month of August in Marculesti ($54 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$) and in the month of September in Marculesti and Braila ($28 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$).

In April the highest value of daily water consumption for sunflowers has been registered at the Băneasa-Giurgiu ($23 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), and in the month of May at Caracal ($35 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in June at Marculesti ($61 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in July at Marculesti ($66 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), and in August at Baneasa - Giurgiu ($48 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$).

The highest values of the water consumption for sugar beet were recorded in Oradea in April ($24 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in Oradea in May ($30 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), at Valu lui Traian in June ($53 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), at Marculesti in July ($62 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), at Baneasa Giurgiu in august ($51 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$) and in Oradea in September ($30 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$).

The highest values of the water consumption for potato were registered as follows: in April at Baneasa-Giurgiu ($20 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in May in Oradea ($31 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in June at Valu lui Traian ($54 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$), in July at Baneasa Giurgiu (56%), in August at Baneasa Giurgiu (37%). In September the potato has been in the vegetation only at Podu Iloaiei ($17 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}/\text{day}$) and Cluj-Napoca ($22 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$). In July, the highest value of the optimum water consumption at maize for silo double crop has been registered at Oradea $44 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$, and in September the highest value has been registered at the Valu Traian, $54 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}/\text{day}$.

The paper emphasized the need of research for establishing the elements used in the irrigation scheduling in the every area for irrigation interesting.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Domuța, C. si colab. *Researches regarding the water requirement in the main crop from Western Romania (1976-2000)*. Proceedings of "19th European Regional Conference, Sustainable use of land and water" 4 – 8 June Brno and Prague (2001).
- [2]. Domuța, C. si colab. *Irrigation influence on sunflower in the conditions of the moderate wet area from Western Romania*, "1st Symposium on Sunflower Industrial Uses", September 11-14, Udine, Italy <http://www.sunflowersymposium.org> (2006).
- [3]. Domuța, C., (coordonator), *Irigațiile în Câmpia Crișurilor 1967 - 2008*. Oradea. Editura Universității din Oradea (2009).
- [4]. Domuța, C. si colab. *Irigarea culturilor în Câmpia Crișurilor*. Oradea. Editura Universității din Oradea (2012).
- [5]. Domuța, Cr., Domuța, C. *Irigarea Porumbului în Câmpia Crișurilor*. Oradea. Editura Universității din Oradea (2010).
- [6]. Domuța, Cr. *Cercetări privind influența irigației asupra culturilor de porumb, soia și sfeclă de zahăr în condițiile Câmpiei Crișurilor*. Teză de doctorat. USAMV Cluj Napoca. (2010).
- [7]. Domuța, Cr. *Subasigurarea cu apă a porumbului, soiei și sfeclei de zahar din Câmpia Crisurilor* Oradea. Editura Universității din Oradea (2011).
- [8]. Domuța, Cr. *Cercetările privind irigarea soiei în Câmpia Crișurilor*. Oradea. Editura Universității din Oradea (2012).
- [9]. Domuța, Cr. (2014). *Research regarding the impact of the correctly irrigation scheduling on soybean from Crisurilor Plain*. Analele Universității Oradea Fascicula Protecția Mediului, Vol XXIII Anul 19 pg.43-51
- [10]. Groza, N., Petrescu, E., Vatamanu, V. *Irigarea culturilor*. Craiova. Editura Sitech Craiova (2004).
- [11]. Grumeza, N., et al. *Corelația consum de apă-producție și prognoza irigației în condițiile pedoclimatice ale Câmpiei de Vest*. Cereale și plante tehnice nr.7/1987. (1987).
- [12]. Grumeza, N., et al. *Prognoza și programarea aplicării udărilor în sistemele de irigații*. București. Editura Ceres (1989).
- [13]. Grumeza, N. Kleps, Cr. *Amenajările de irigații din România*. București. Editura Ceres. (2005).

- [14]. Ionescu Șișești, Vl. *Consumul de apă și regimul de apă al culturilor*. București. Editura Ceres (1982).
- [15]. Ionescu Șișești, Vl. *Irigarea culturilor*. București. Editura Ceres (1986).
- [16]. Luca, E., Nagy, Z. *Irigarea culturilor*. Cluj-Napoca. Editura Genesis Tipo (1999).
- [17]. Muntean, L.S., Borcean, I., Axinte, M., Roman Gh.V. *Fitotehnie*. Editura Ion Ionescu de la Brad. (2001).
- [18]. Muntean, L.S., et al , *Fitotehnie*. Cluj-Napoca. Editura Academic Press . (2008).
- [19]. Petrescu, E. *Cercetări privind reducerea consumului de apă la cultura de sfeclă de zahăr irigată în condițiile pedoclimatice ale Câmpiei Caracalului*. Teză de doctorat. ASAS “Gheorghe Ionescu Șișești”, București (1999).

THE WINE TOURISM POTENTIAL OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

Boris GĂINĂ¹, Eugen ALEXANDROV²

Abstract. *The tourism potential of the Republic of Moldova, is varied, offering a wide range of tourist attractions. Wine tourism is one of the priority sectors of the national agricultural tourism, which by its resources and through interconnections with other branches of the national economy, is an important factor for economic progress. Efficient use of wine tourism in the interest of the national economy is a chance for Moldova's development.*

Keywords: entities, itinerary, wine tourism.

The tourism potential of the Republic of Moldova, is extremely varied, offering a large gamut of tourist attractions. The wine tourism is one of the priority sectors of the national agricultural tourism, which by its resources and through interconnections with other branches of the national economy, is a significant factor for economic progress. Efficient use of wine tourism in the interest of the national economy is a chance for Moldova's development.[4]

In the autumn of 2004 was drafted Republic of Moldova wine tourism itinerary which includes the six trails selected and thoroughly substantiated.[3] In this arsenal of general the cultural heritage of the country have been identified at the time entities known wineries: „Cricova SA”, „Mileștii Mici”, „Purcari”, „Barza albă” (Bălți), „Cojușna”, „Ciumai”, „Aur vin” (Vulcănești) (fig. 1.) [1].

Currently, this wine tourism itinerary has assessed primarily by completing considerably the visits to wineries, cellars and underground galleries to complement the collections of young wines, sparkling wines and cognacs from Chateau Vartely (Orhei), Fautor (Tigheci), Garling (Ungheni), Vinăria din Vale

Fig. 1. The tourist trail to the best known wineries of southern of the Republic of Moldova.

¹ acad., Agricultural Sciences Section of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova;
Academy of Romania Scientists, Splaiul Independenței 54, 050094, Bucharest, Romania.

² Ph.D., Institute of Genetics, Physiology and Plant Protection of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova

(Slobozia mare), Vierul Vin (s.Burlacu r-nul Cahul), Asconi (Puhoi), Vinăria Calarași, Castelul Mimi (Anenii Noi), Cimișlia Wineries, Shervin (Ialoveni), Maurt (Chișinău-Nisporeni), Kazayak Vin, Migdal P (Chișinău-Cojușna), Mold Nord (Fălești), Struguraș (Nisporeni), Sălcuța (Căușeno), Suvorov Vin (Cahul) and other [5].

A good example of high in wine culture is represented by production units of high quality of small producers Association: Et cetera (Crocmaz), Mezalimpe (Ștefan Vodă), Minis terrios (Chișinău), Vinăria Poiana (Ulmu) and other.

In the visits captivating in collections and production halls were attache presentations of industrial plantations (100-200 ha) and medium (10-20 hectares) of vines, occupied with European varieties of the species *Vitis vinifera* L. (Chardonnay, Sauvignon, Riesling de Rhin, Muscat Ottonel - whietes, Merlot, Cabarnet- Sauvignon, Pino noir - red), but also from autochthonous classic (Feteasca Albă, Feteasca neagră, Rara neagră) and new varieties of national selection (Legenda, Riton Luminița, Viorica, Muscat de Ialoveni and other) [2].

The tourists from abroad as well as in the country with a strong interest visiting the plantations of the „Cricova” SA from the district Criuleni and the district Gahul (Lucești), „Mileștii Mici”, „Cojușna Vin”, „Chateau Vartely”, Maurt (Nisporeni), „Vinuri de Comrat”, „Garling” , „Salcuța”, „Purcari”, „Migdal P”, „Kazayak Vin”, „Călărași Vin”, „Asconi” and many others that are the exploited to a high level agro similar to those from the European wine-growing countries.

Another object of the wine tourism the entities of the Modern nurseries are the re-equipped with the most advanced equipment, endowed with the most progressive methods of grafting-stratification-toughening-planting machines-care, such as „Cojușna Vin”, „Elvitis-Com” and other.

The guests Republic of Moldova participate greatly to national holidays "National Day of Wine" (September each year), vernissage of wine (every semester year), organized by the National Office of Vine and Wine, Exhibition "Vin Moldova", organized by the Union of Oenologists and Poliproject Exhibitions Ltd, the Feast of table grapes (Chimișlia, September each year) etc.

Currently the are available for visitors and state units, which provide important services winegrowers and winemakers in the analysis of grapes and wines: National Center for Alcohol Production Verification Enology Laboratory, Technical University of Moldova, Laboratory of Quality Control Wine Production from Scientific and Practical Institute for Horticulture and Food Technologies.

At the Academy of Sciences of Moldova has been created the Collection *Vitis* with varieties Balkan-Black Sea Region, which along with other collections present a vast intellectual interest.

Among the most urgent problems in boosting of wine tourism are: improving financial climate, improving of infrastructure, roads, access roads, raise

the level sanitary routes and agroboarding house, staff training, enhancing the quality of services of any kind (accommodation, translation, translator, food, currency exchange, tastings, purchases of souvenirs and gifts etc.).

Fig. 2. The national tourist route "Kingdom of Moldovan wines"

Fig. 3. The national tourist route "On the wine road in Southeast Moldova"

REFERENCES

- [1] Ciumac, Jorj, Deseatnicov Olga., Găină Boris. *Organizarea producerii și deservirii în unitățile de alimentație publică. Servirea vinurilor*. Material didactic. UTM, 1999.
- [2] Găină Boris - *Via, vinul și civilizația*. Monografie Chișinău, 2000.
- [3] Găină Boris, Dabija N. *Drumul vinului în Moldova*; Dep. Dezvoltarea Turismului al Republicii. Moldova. – Chișinău : S. n., 2004. – 24 p.
- [4] Legea Republicii Moldova Nr. 352 din 24.11.2006 cu privire la organizarea și desfășurarea activității turistice în Republica Moldova. Publicat: 02.02.2007 în Monitorul Oficial Nr. 14-17 art Nr : 40
- [5] <https://ru.scribd.com/document/155920879/Turism-Vitivinicol>

DANUBE DELTA. ECONOMIC RESOURCES

Aurel LUP¹, Liliana MIRON², Indira Deniz ALIM²

Abstract: *The Danube Delta, with an area of 430,000 ha, is one of the largest in the world – i.e. ranking the 22nd in the world and the 3rd in Europe. Since 1980, the Danube Delta has been a Biosphere Reserve, and, in 1990, the Romanian government declared it the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve. From the very beginning, for Romania, the Danube Delta was an important economic resource; fish, pasture, wood, reed and, in recent years, tourism represent the main economic resources of the Danube Delta. In the second half of the 50's (twentieth century), the Romanian Government decided to use reed as raw material for papermaking; thus, the Delta was organized according to this purpose. There were also created special machines and equipment for harvesting and transporting reed. Because the reed proved to be an expensive raw material, after 10 years, this activity was waived. In the following period, agriculture received greater attention. The compartments designed in order to grow reed would be drained and converted into farms on surfaces exceeding 200,000 ha. However, only an area of about 30,000 ha was drained, where agriculture and especially businesses are still practiced nowadays. Currently, it is attempted to harmonize the various activities and resources of the Danube Delta: fisheries, agriculture, forestry and, of course, tourism. Activities are conducted for the further systematization of the territory and localities, in order to improve the living standard of Delta inhabitants.*

Keywords: agriculture, the Danube Delta, reed culture, reserve, tourism.

1.INTRODUCTION

As a physical geographical unit, the Danube Delta represents the area between the three arms through which the Danube flows into the Black Sea, i.e. Chilia, Sulina and St. Gheorghe. The area of over 430 thousand hectares places it among the largest deltas of the planet, i.e. the 22nd in the world and 3rd in Europe, and, with the lagoons complex Razelm-Sinoe, it is one of the largest wetlands.

As an ecological resource, the Danube Delta is important both in terms of stretch (51.0% of Tulcea County and 27.9% of Dobrogea region) and of the richness, variety and specificity of its resources. The work *Danube Delta Reed Monograph* [1] presents a distribution of Delta land uses in the 60s, as follows: pisciculture - 323,100 ha; reed crop and pisciculture - 213,900 ha; agriculture - 62,300 ha;

¹ Academy of Romanian Scientists , Splaiul Independenței 54, 050094, Bucharest, Romania.
E-mail: luparel@yahoo.com

² Ovidius University of Constanta, Romania

forestry - 18,800 ha; land within the built-up area, dam-bank areas and coastal belt - 17,800 ha.

In administrative terms, the Danube Delta belongs to Tulcea County, situated in Dobrogea, the South East Development Region no. 2. A significant historical milestone is represented by the 17th of October 1957, when the last collective farm was established in Chilia Veche, in the Danube Delta, ending thus the collectivization campaign in Dobrogea [2].

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

The material used in this paper is bibliographical and it represents a synthesis of several works published by different authors, from the 2nd half of the twentieth century to the present. In our perspective, this communication can raise the scientific community's interest, both at national and international levels. Currently, the Danube Delta is important both in terms of the variety and richness of its resources but also as a study topic, being one of the largest wetlands in Europe and worldwide.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The reed crop. In the Danube Delta, the reed grows naturally, almost on the entire surface (except levees and water surface), i.e. almost 300 thousand ha. In the past, the reed was harvested in relatively small amounts, i.e. 10 to 15 thousand tons annually, and it was used more in home economics or as raw material for reed plates (about 60%). The reed problem had concerned the authorities for about 15 years (1950-1965), the exploitation of this (more or less agricultural) natural resource being the main economic activity in the Danube Delta, and the extent, intensity and means of action were one among the most barbaric human intervention in a space that would become *the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve*, part of the world cultural heritage, under UNESCO protection.

The exploitation of reed in the Danube Delta started in the second half of the 50s, after the Congress VII of the Romanian Communist Party had set the task to develop the cellulose and paper industry, particularly by using the reed in the Danube Delta. At that time, there were already some studies and even experiments on reed biology, estimated production, harvesting technology, storage and transport to the processing industry.

The industrial reed production grew rapidly, from 6,500 t in 1956 to almost 60,000 t in 1959-1960; 110,000 t in 1960-1961 and 226,000 t in 1964-1965. The end of the industrial exploitation of reed took place in the period 1965-1970, when the whole activity was abandoned due to high operating and transport costs.

However, embankments, dams, locks, artwork, and rusty components of the famous machinery systems, which became museum pieces, remained (Photo 1).

3.2. *The Danube Delta and agriculture.*

Agricultural activities have accompanied fishing since ancient times, because many levees were primarily rich in pastures, which allowed the growth of a large number of animals, sheep, pigs, and cattle, some even in a semi-wild regime. In higher areas, the delta inhabitants cultivated cereals and food plants. In 1965, the agriculture in the Danube Delta occupied an area of 62,300 ha [4].

Photo 1. Equipment for reed harvest (4).

However, during the command economy period, after the reed bankruptcy, the Delta's agricultural vocation was rediscovered; among others, it would play a

priority role in the Delta economy, becoming the ultimate source for the increase in arable land, which was one of the agricultural obsessions of the totalitarian regime. For this purpose, the former dammed areas used in reed production were just right to become polders for intensive agriculture. Some of these areas were to be drained, the reed was to be removed and then they would be equipped for irrigation.

The drained premises would become large state farms, producing grain, industrial crops, but also growing livestock: cattle and sheep. No less than 218 300 ha were scheduled to enter the agricultural circuit, of which over 50% were already dammed.

Photo 2. Project for agricultural activity in the Danube Delta

The first and ultimately the only drained area was Pardina, with 28,970 ha. In 1980-1981, a multidisciplinary team of researchers from the Institute of Agricultural Economics, the Academy of Agricultural Sciences and Forestry, drafted the project for the organization of Pardina as an agricultural state enterprise. The author of this paper participated in this project. A final version of the structure for agricultural use in the planned economy era was the *Program for the full equipping and operation of the Danube Delta*, developed by ISPIF, in 1982, and approved by the State Council Decree no. 92/1983; the agricultural area would increase to 144,000 ha, of which 94,000 would be equipped for irrigation and 50,000 hectares would represent improved natural pastures. The number of animals was to reach 20 thousand cattle, 350 thousand sheep, 120 thousand pigs and 350 thousand birds.

After 1989, at the inaugural Conference of the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve [5], the report of the conference on agriculture mentioned: agricultural land in the reserve - 62,000 ha, of which 53,000 ha in the polders; 4,800 ha of private agricultural land and 19,500 ha of communal pastures. In the Delta, there were also 19,000 cows, 6,000 sheep and 45,000 pigs.

3.3. Pisciculture. The evolution of the fish yield in the Danube Delta took a course similar to that at the national level. In 1960, the catch represented about 3,000 t; in 1988, it reached a peak of almost 92,000 t, while in 2010 the yield fell to 15,184 t (Figure 1).

In the Danube Delta, the fish yield increased from 5,400 t annually in the period 1947-1956 (yield of 16.3 kg/ha) to 14,000 t by 1990, decreasing to about 5,500 t in 1992 [5].

The report presented at the inaugural Conference of 1993 on the *Management Programmed of the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve* [5] mentioned some figures on the evolution of the fish yield in fish farms from the Danube Delta, which, at that time, had an area of about 36,000 ha. Here also the annual quantity of the fish caught was reduced from 9,000 t to 3,710 t in only five years.

More concrete data are shown in the graph in Figure 2 [6]. From a yield valued at 8,000 t in 1973, it reached 1,600 – 1,700 t in 1993. These data were provided by the statistics of industrial fishing in the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve. It is noted that the structure of catches reflects only a part of the fish fauna within the delta, the commercial catches respectively, i.e. about 25% of the species existing in the reserve.

Figure 2. Evolution of the fish yield per total species, in the Danube Delta, during 1973-1993

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the structure of the main species. The largest share is held by less valuable species, such as the crucian, whose share is growing; species such as the bream or the roach are shrinking. Instead, more valuable species, such as the pike, the perch and the tench, almost disappeared. As far as the sturgeon species are concerned, they no longer appear in the structure. An assessment of the sturgeon yield in the Romanian Danube River and Delta, made by the researchers from the Delta Institute, approximates 250 t/year during 1951-1955, about 50 t/year during 1981-1985 and only 20 t/year after 1990.

Figure 3. The evolution of the main fish species in Romania, during 1973-1993

All the figures presented to the media and the statistics are approximate. The reasons for the lack of confidence in the official statistics of the fish catch in the Danube Delta are explained by the researchers at the Delta Institute.

Until 1990-1992, the main source of error was represented by the assessment of self-consumption quantities. The emergence of private trade alongside the state sector created a black market valued at 2500-2600 t/year [7].

The black market prices were five times higher than those of state companies. In 1996, for example, the value of the fish sold on the black market was estimated at 50 billion lei, while the fishermen's risks were

Photo 3. The fishery a great riches of the Danube Delta

minimal or nonexistent.

The number of the tools used by fishermen is also much higher than the one received from trade companies: around 1.7 times in pots, 3.3 times in fishing nets, 2.9 times in seines [7]. The catch structure is also distorted, i.e. the valuable species representing 20-25% of the catch are not mentioned in statistics.

Aquaculture or farmed fish. In the Danube Delta, the first fish farms were established in 1961 on an area of 560 ha. This area grew to over 30,000 ha in 1974, to 36,000-39,000 ha in the early 90s and to 49,000-50,000 around the 2000s.

If the agricultural development programs – in terms of area – were met, the pisciculture farm development remains an open subject due to the poor results obtained in terms of productivity. The yield in fish farms is between 100-200 kg/ha, while the yield of the carp under natural conditions exceeds 700 kg/ha.

3.4. Other economic resources of the Danube Delta. The fish, the reed, the plant and the animal agricultural products, the exploitable wood are natural resources of the Delta, even if each is accompanied by human impact – i.e. specific technologies that can increase their value and profitability. It is obvious that this impact must have certain limits in order to ensure sustainability, which, essentially, consists in short term operation, in order to achieve a natural balance – i.e. the preservation of the environment useful to the human being and of the environment as a whole, as a condition necessary to the survival of the human species.

Forest and wood. In the structure of delta utilities, forestry, with its remaining 6,642 ha of the 23,000 ha existing in the early 90s, is a priceless ecological wealth. An area of 5,104 ha (the Letea Forest – 3,644 ha; the Caraorman Forest – 893 ha and the Erenciuc Forest – 567 ha) represents nature reserves, classified as *natural monuments, nature reserves, ancient forests of special value* [7].

Delta fauna. It includes 75 fish species (including sturgeon), 280 bird species – some of them classified as natural monuments –, mammals – from boars to ermines and reptiles.

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The Danube Delta, with an area of 430 hectares, is one of the largest in Europe and in the world, with the status of Biosphere Reserve; it is one of Romania's greatest riches; unfortunately, it is neglected or poorly managed.
- (2) In time, instead of harmonizing and using the multitude of riches (some extremely rare or unique), priority was given to only one of the resources that

could be exploited economically: fish, reed, agricultural production, neglecting the most valuable ones, i.e. the rich fauna and flora.

- (3) The fish – the dominant resource of an aquatic environment – was exploited intensively, uncontrollably, until depletion, reaching the ridiculous yield of 10-20 kg/ ha and the disappearance or depletion of valuable species (official statistics confirm the evolution of the phenomenon).
- (4) Reed was another resource whose exploitation subdivided the Delta by dikes and equipped it with unique equipment, entailing huge investments; however, after 10 years, the business was abandoned, but not before destroying the biological basis of reed regeneration.
- (5) Agriculture is practiced on an area of about 60,000 ha in various forms: intensive, organic, traditional-primitive for the subsistence of its inhabitants. For many Romanian and foreign investors, agriculture remains a profitable business, not without a negative impact on the biosphere reserve status.
- (6) The attempts of the Danube Delta Institute to restore the natural environment of the Delta are hindered even nowadays by the refusal of the government protectors of the great agricultural domestic and foreign barons from the Danube Valley.
- (7) At present, instead of using it under the world Biosphere Reserve status, the Delta is the heaven of all kinds of greedy investors, who want to make profit and to get rich overnight, who see the delta as the last entertainment field.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hâncu S., Jeleu I., Codreanu M.M., (coord.) 2009: *Dunărea, Lunca și Delta Dunării. Agricultură și mediu. Prezent și perspectivă*. Ed. BREN, București.
- [2] Lup A., 2012: *40 de ani de agricultură socialistă în Dobrogea*. Ed. Ex Ponto, Constanța.
- [3] Lup A., 2014: *Agricultura socialistă a României: 1949-1989. Mit și realitate*. Ed. Ex Ponto, Constanța.
- [4] Rudescu I., Niculescu C., Chiru S.C., 1965: *Monografia stufului în Delta Dunării*. Ed. Academiei Republicii Populare Române, București.
- [5] x x x: *Programul de Management al mediului privind Rezervația Biosferei Delta Dunării – 1993*. Tulcea.
- [6] x x x: *Analele științifice ale Institutului Delta Dunării*, 1995, Tulcea.
- [7] x x x: *Anale științifice ale Institutului Delta Dunării* 1997, Tulcea

LONGEVITY OF RESEEDED GRASS SPECIES USED FOR RESTORING THE DEGRADED SUBALPINE MEADOWS

Teodor MARUȘCA^{1,2}, Vasile A. BLAJ¹, Vasile MOCANU¹

Abstract. *In the summer of 1996, a degraded grassland, invaded by *Nardus stricta* species, located at 1800 m altitude from subalpine level of the Bucegi Mountains, after total herbicide with glyphosate, liming using CaO at 2/3 Ah (in the autumn of 1995) and paddocking with sheep (5 nights, 1 sheep / m²) has been over-seeded or reseeded. The grass seed mixture was composed of *Phleum pratense* 40%; *Festuca pratensis* 25%; *Lolium perenne* 5%, *Lotus corniculatus* 15% and *Trifolium hybridum* 15%. A part of the variants have been fertilized with chemical fertilizers with doses of N 150 K P50 50 kg / ha and others plots have been fertilized with organic fertilizer by a paddocking system applied before of reseeded grassland establishment. In 2004 and 2011 an organic fertilizing by cattle paddocking, has been practiced. The reseeded species that do not reach maturity remain a much longer period of time than is known in the technical literature, this being 2-3 times higher in the high mountains than in the lowlands and hills. In the grassy carpet the *Phleum pratense* species survives in large proportion, even after 20 years of sowing.*

Keywords: degraded grassland, fertilizer, herbicide, over-seeding, reseeded.

INTRODUCTION

The mountain pastures, used by grazing for many years, are exposed to processes of degradation of floristic composition, if not properly maintained, fertilized and used rationally [1].

By applying the organic (paddocking system) and chemical fertilizers, degraded mountain grasslands, invaded by strict *Nardus stricta* species, can turn into valuable pastures, dominated by *Festuca rubra* and *Agrostis capillaris* [4]

¹ Research and Development Institute for Grasslands, 5 Cucului Str., 500128, 0268472701; fax 0268475295, www.pajisti-grassland.ro, office@pajisti-grassland.ro

² Academy of Romania Scientists, Splaiul Independenței 54, 050094, Bucharest, Romania

One of the most effective ways to improve *Nardus stricta* degraded grasslands is by total sward destruction (herbicides, harrowing, milling, plowing, etc.), followed by the establishment of reseeded pastures with high quality and production [2]

Such research work to improve more effectively the *Nardus stricta* grasslands has been conducted in sub-alpine altitudinal level in the last 20 years [3].

One such long-term research activity in sub-alpine level was possible to determine the survival duration of some species of perennial sown grasses that it is different from the conditions at lower altitudinal levels, thematic presented in this paper.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

At the Research Mountain Grasslands Base from the Bucegi Massive, located at 1,800 m of altitude on a degraded pasture, with participation of *Nardus stricta* species over 60%, in the autumn of 1996, the grassy carpet was sprayed with 5 L/ha Roundup product (glyphosate). After two weeks were applied 7.5 tons per ha of lime (CaO) to correct 2/3 Ah of soil acidity (hydrolytic acidity).

In June 1996, after sheep climbing on the mountain, it paddocked a sheep 5 nights/1 m², after which the land was harrowing at 2-3 cm deep and sown with a mixture of: *Phleum pratense* 40% *Festuca pratensis* 25% *Lolium perenne* 5%, *Lotus corniculatus* 15% and *Trifolium hybridum* 15%, all missing species of wild flora.

In the organic fertilized variant, paddocking was repeated, at the same rate, with sheep in 2004, and with cows in 2012. Similarly, for comparison, the same mixture of grasses with chemical fertilizers N 150 P 50 K 50 kg / ha, during 1996-1998, 2004-2006 and 2012-2014, was fertilized.

After sampling for dry matter (DM) and chemical analysis, pasture was used by grazing with cows. The sown species were not able to multiply by self-seeding, because they have not reached maturity. Annually, between 1997-2016, flora observations using the KLAPP-ELEMBERG method of participation percentage in phytomass, were made.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following the floristic observations, over 20 years, every two years, it was possible an overview of the dynamics of the sown and spontaneous species in the chemical fertilized variant (Table 1.).

From this data follows the best representation of sown species of 86% was on 1999-2000 and the lowest of 21% in 2011-2012. The basic *Phleum pratense* species was maintained at a rate of 21-66% in grassy carpet, being the only species that has resisted for 20 years. The remaining species have disappeared at

different times, namely: *Festuca pratensis* after 12 years, *Lolium perenne* after 4 years, *Trifolium hybridum* after 10 years and *Lotus corniculatus* after 8 years.

In the grassy carpet the *Poa pratensis* species appears, from spontaneous flora, only after 15 years from the start of the improvement work and *Taraxacum officinale* after 7 years.

The pastoral value of reseeded pastures, chemically fertilized, is 61-83 and it is good to very good. On variant organic fertilized by paddocking system, the success of sown species is better than chemical fertilization, being 90% in the period 1997-1998 and 22% in 2015-2016 (Table 2).

In the 20 years of observations, the only species that survived in this case was the *Phleum pratense* species, in a variable proportion of 22-55%. In this case *Festuca pratensis* disappeared after 16 years, *Lolium perenne* after 6 years and the *Trifolium hybridum* species after 10 years, a little more enduring than the chemically fertilized variant.

Instead, in the paddocked variant, in the first year, from spontaneous flora, the *Taraxacum officinale* has established and after the 7th year *Poa pratensis* has maintained around 5%. The pastoral value of the organic variant has indices between 74 and 90, being superior to the chemical alternative.

A comparison of the influence of the type of chemical to organic fertilizer is presented in Table 3. These data show that the organic fertilization has favored the sown species *Phleum pratense*, *Festuca pratensis* and *Trifolium hybridum* and the spontaneous species *Trifolium repens* and *Poa pratensis*. The viability of the sown species, fertilized organically is longer than the chemical variant, by 2 years for *Lolium perenne* and 4 years for *Festuca pratensis*.

Similarly, in the organic variant, the *Poa pratensis* species appears faster by 8 years and *Taraxacum officinale* by 6 years compared to the chemical solution. In general, the index of forage value of organic variant is higher by 9 than the chemical variant.

Table 1
The evolution of the floristic composition of sown pastures, fertilized chemically, Blana- Bucegi Mountains 1997 - 2016
(% Participation in aboveground phytomass)

Specii	1997- 1998	1999- 2000	2001- 2002	2003- 2004	2005- 2006	2007- 2008	2009- 2010	2011- 2012	2013- 2014	2015- 2016
SOWN SPECIES	64	86	53	57	55	37	29	21	34	24
Perennial grasses										
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	30	66	41	45	49	33	29	21	34	24
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	12	4	2	2	4	4
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	9	+
Perennial forage legumes										
<i>Trifolium hybridum</i>	12	16	10	10	2
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	1	+	+	+
SPONTANEOUS SPECIES	36	14	47	43	45	63	71	79	66	76
Perennial grasses										
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	8	4	15	14	17	33	34	27	20	23
<i>Festuca nigrescens</i>	7	1	12	8	5	6	8	11	14	9
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	1	3	4
Alte graminee	16	3	7	10	9	11	15	21	13	21
Perennial forage legumes										
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	4	4	10	6	7	10	11	10	7	10
Others families										
<i>Ligusticum mutelina</i>	+	1	+	+	1	2	2	5	3	4
<i>Potentilla ternata</i>	1	+	+	1	1	1	1	2	5	2
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	.	.	.	+	2	+	+	1	+	+
Alte specii	+	1	3	4	3	+	+	1	1	3
PASTORAL VALUE	77	83	77	76	78	73	68	61	67	62

Table 2
 The evolution of the floristic composition of sown pastures, organic fertilized by paddocking, Blana- Bucegi Mountains, 1997 - 2016
 (% Participation in aboveground phytomass)

Species	1997- 1998	1999- 2000	2001- 2002	2003- 2004	2005- 2006	2007- 2008	2009- 2010	2011- 2012	2013- 2014	2015- 2016
SOWN SPECIES	90	76	52	56	67	53	29	24	24	22
Perennial grasses										
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	22	33	35	45	55	42	25	23	24	22
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	20	7	3	6	10	11	4	1	.	.
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	9	1	+
Perennial forage legumes										
<i>Trifolium hybridum</i>	38	35	14	5	2
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	1	+	+
SPONTANEOUS SPECIES	10	24	48	44	33	47	71	76	76	78
Perennial grasses										
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	1	8	12	13	17	28	34	32	20	25
<i>Festuca nigrescens</i>	1	1	1	5	1	+	1	1	2	5
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	.	.	.	2	3	4	5	4	5	5
Other grasses	2	1	14	8	2	1	5	8	5	8
Perennial forage legumes										
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	6	13	14	12	8	8	16	22	30	24
Others families										
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	+	+	1	2	1	2	5	4	7	5
<i>Ligusticum mutelina</i>	+	1	2	1	1	2	3	3	3	3
<i>Potentilla ternata</i>	+	+	1	1	+	1	1	1	2	1
Others species	+	+	3	+	+	1	1	1	2	1
PASTORAL VALUE	90	88	76	82	89	84	76	75	79	74

Table 3
Comparative data on the effect of fertilizer on species type and their longevity in the grassy carpet Blana - Bucegi 1997 – 2016

Specii	Semănat 1996	Media 1997 - 2016		Dif. + -		Durată specie (ani)		
		Chimic	Organic	Chimic	Organic	Chimic	Organic	Dif. + -
SOWN SPECIES	100	46,0	49,3	+3,3				
Perennial grasses								
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	40	37,2	32,6	-4,6		20	20	0
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	25	2,8	6,2	+3,4		12	16	+4
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	5	0,9	1,0	+0,1		4	6	+2
Perennial forage legumes								
<i>Trifolium hybridum</i>	15	5,0	9,4	+4,4		10	10	0
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	15	0,1	0,1	0		8	6	-2
SPONTANEOUS SPECIES	0	54,0	50,7	-3,3				
Perennial grasses								
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	X	19,5	19,0	-0,5		20	20	0
<i>Festuca nigrescens</i>	X	8,1	1,9	-6,2		20	20	0
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	X	0,8	2,8	+2,0		6	14	+8
Other grasses	X	12,6	5,4	-7,2		20	20	0
Perennial forage legumes								
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	X	7,9	15,3	+7,4		20	20	0
Others families								
<i>Ligusticum mutelina</i>	X	1,8	1,9	+0,1		20	20	0
<i>Potentilla ternata</i>	X	1,4	0,8	-0,6		20	20	0
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	X	0,3	2,7	+2,4		14	20	+6
Others species	X	1,6	0,9	-0,7		20	20	0
PASTORAL VALUE	94	72	81	+9		X	X	X

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) In the sub-alpine high mountains are few species of perennial grasses and forage legumes adapted to these soil and climate conditions, less favorable to plant growth;
- (2) By providing optimal conditions of soil and fertilizer, timothy (*Phleum pratense*) manages to survive more than 20 years at a rate of 37% in the chemical fertilizer variant and 33% in organic fertilization (paddock) compared to 40% at sowing;
- (3) The longevity of perennial sown grasses and legumes at high mountain altitude is at least double than those sown at lower altitude in the plains;
- (4) Paddock by animals has favored the sown species *Festuca pratensis* and *Trifolium hybridum* compared to the chemical fertilization that has favored the *Phleum pratense* species;
- (5) From spontaneous flora *Poa pratensis*, *Trifolium repens* and *Taraxacum officinale* are stimulated by paddocking and *Festuca nigrescens* by chemical fertilization.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bărbulescu, Motcă Gh., 1983, *Pășunile munților înalți*, Ed. Ceres, București
- [2] Marușca T., 1977, *Sisteme de înființare a pajiștilor temporare pe suprafețele dominate de *Nardus stricta**, Lucrări științifice ale SCCP Măgurele – Brașov, vol. III, pp. 35-49, Redacția material de propagandă agricolă, București
- [3] Marușca T., Andreoiu Andreea, Blaj V.A., Mocanu V., Haș C.E, *Long term effect of improvement methods on subalpine degraded *Nardus stricta* l. grasslands*, 2015, Academy of Romanian Scientists, Annals Series on Agriculture, Silviculture and Veterinary Medicine Sciences, vol. 4. nr 1-2, București, pp.42-49, ISSN 2069 - 1149
- [4] Pușcaru D., Pușcaru-Soroceanu E., Paucă A., Șerbănescu I., Beldie Al., Ștefureac Tr., Cernescu N., Saghin N., Crețu V., Lupan L., Tașcenco V., 1956, *Pășunile alpine din Munții Bucegi*, Ed. Academiei Republicii Populare Române

TRENDS IN ROMANIA'S POULTRY MEAT MARKET IN THE PERIOD 2007-2015

Agatha POPESCU¹

Abstract. *The paper analyzed the main trends in Romania's poultry meat market based on the data provided by the National Institute of Statistics for the period 2007-2015. Romania has a high potential for producing poultry meat, ranking on the 7th position in the EU-28. The poultry slaughtered weight increased both due to the number of slaughtered poultry and the average weight at slaughter. The chickens have the highest share in poultry live weight and carcass weight. Poultry meat is on the top position, representing about 50% of the meat consumption per inhabitant. The consumption is covered both by the domestic production and imports. However, the export/import ratio is less than 1, reflecting that Romania is a net importing country of poultry meat. To surpass the pressure of the foreign competitors, the Romanian producers of poultry meat must assure a high genetic value biological material, high quality and sufficient feeding, production cost reduction, and to intensify exports.*

Keywords: trends, meat, market, poultry, Romania not more than five.

1. Introduction

Poultry meat is a healthy meat with a high nutritional value given by the high quality protein content and low cholesterol percentage. Consumers are aware of this and for this reason consumption has increased. More than this, it could be produced in the shortest period of time compared to pork, beef and other meat sorts, and the production costs are covered by the market price assuring a high return and profitability to poultry breeders in the integrated industrialized companies [1].

The EU is an important poultry meat producer, but also an exporter and importer. As poultry meat consumption is increasing, the European and international market need a higher supply of poultry meat. Poultry farming in the developing countries is a chance to eradicate hungry [7].

Romania has a good position among the EU producers, regarding the poultry livestock, the number of slaughtered poultry and slaughtered weight [5, 6]. The poultry meat sector is continuously developing mainly in industrial specialized units with a modern technical endowment, where the best technologies are applied and production performance is high. Also, poultry farming is

¹ Academy of Romania Scientists, Splaiul Independenței 54, 050094, Bucharest, Romania

developed in small individual holdings, but their share in meat production is smaller compared to the specialized companies [2].

In this context, the paper aimed to analyze the dynamics of poultry meat production, consumption and trade in order to identify the main trends and measures destined to develop the sector and keep the pace with the market pressures.

2. Materials and Methods

The study is based on the empirical data collected from the National Institute of Statistics Data base, Tempo Online for the period 2007-2015.

The main studied indicators characterizing poultry meat market have been the following ones: weight of poultry for slaughtering and consumption at the national level, the live weight of slaughtered poultry in industrial specialized units, the chickens slaughtered live weight, the poultry meat contribution to meat production, poultry meat supply, poultry meat consumption, poultry meat export and import, farm gate price per kilogram poultry live weight, and Romania's position regarding the number of slaughtered poultry and the slaughtered live weight.

The data were processed using the modern usual methods such as: time analysis using fixed basis indices, comparison method, descriptive statistics of the main studied indicators. The obtained results are tabled and interpreted.

3. Results and discussions

3.1 Weight of poultry for slaughtering and consumption

The weight of poultry for slaughtering and consumption increased by 34.1% from 416 thousand tons in 2007 to 558 thousand tons in 2015.

The increasing trend of the slaughtered weight was due to the increased number of slaughtered chicken.

This was possible grace to the industrialized poultry meat sector which is vertically integrated mainly in the competitive production units including reproduction units, incubation, broilers fattening units, slaughterhouses, and own shops for selling the poultry meat products directly to consumers [3].

An important aspect is the fact that the industrial specialized units slaughter more and more poultry with a deep and positive impact on the poultry meat production. In this respect, if in 2007, there were 281 thousand tons of poultry slaughtered weight in the industrial specialized units, in 2015, this indicator reached 515 thousand tons, being by 83.2% higher than in 2007 (Table 1).

Table 1. Weight of poultry for slaughtering and consumption in Romania in the period 2007-2015 (Thousand tons)

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2015/2007 %
Poultry Weight	416	410	489	446	477	471	457	488	558	134.1
Poultry weight slaughtered in indus. spec. units	281	340	401	392	405	430	449	475	515	183.2

Source: Own calculation based on the NIS Data base, 2016 [4].

This was the consequence of the increased contribution of the industrial specialized units to slaughtered poultry weight from 67.5% in 2007 to 92.2% in 2015.

3.2. The chickens slaughtered weight

Another important aspect is that the slaughtered chickens in industrial specialized units increased by 77.9% from 275 thousand tons in 2007 to 489.7 thousand tons in 2015 and the contribution of chickens live weight to the total poultry slaughtered weight is very high, about 97% (Table 2).

Table 2. Poultry slaughtered live weight in the industrial specialized units in Romania in the period 2007-2015 (Thousand tons)

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2015/2007 %
Poultry weight in ind. spec. units	416	410	489	446	477	471	457	488	558	134.1
Chickens	281	340	401	392	405	430	449	475	515	183.2

Source: Own calculation based on the NIS Data base, 2016 [4].

This is due to the fact that chickens represent 97.5% of the total number of slaughtered poultry in the industrial specialized units and their average weight at slaughter is 2.2 kg/head equal to the average weight at slaughter for all the slaughtered poultry (Table 3).

Table 3. Number of poultry slaughtered in the industrial specialized units in Romania in the period 2007-2015 (Thousand heads)

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2015/2007 %
Total number of slaughtered poultry	131.4	154.7	186.4	175.9	182	198.6	207.4	213.5	229.6	174.7
Chickens	128.9	153.2	185.5	175.0	180	196.6	204.6	211.2	224.0	173.6

Source: Own calculation based on the NIS Data base, 2016 [4].

In 2007, the highest share of slaughtered poultry was recorded in S Muntenia 28.9%, N E 18.6% and Central part of Romania 16.1%. In 2015, the contribution of the micro development regions was registered in S E Romania 24.3%, N E 22.7%, S Muntenia 19.4%, Central region 13.6% and N West 11% [4].

3.3. The poultry carcass weight

The poultry carcass weight increased by 77.2% from 211 thousand tons in 2007 to 374 thousand tons in 2015.

Table 4. The poultry carcass weight in the industrial specialized units in Romania in the period 2007-2015 (Thousand tons)

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2015/2007 %
Carcass weight	211.4	255.7	300	287.4	292.8	312.8	332.8	346.1	374.7	177.2
Chickens	206.4	252.1	298	283.9	284.8	301.8	322.2	334.7	355.7	172.3

Source: Own calculation based on the NIS Data base, 2016 [4].

The chickens' carcass weight carried out in the industrial specialized units increased by 72.3% from 206.4 thousand tons in 2007 to 355.7% thousand tons in 2015. As a result, the contribution of chickens to the carcass weight recorded a slight decline from 97.6% in 2007 to 94.9% in 2015 (Table 4).

3.4. The poultry contribution to meat production

The poultry contribution to meat production places poultry on the top position. In 2015, the structure of Romania's meat production included: poultry meat 49.38%, pork 43.54%, bovine meat 5.86% and sheep and goat meat 1.22% [4].

3.5. The poultry meat supply

The poultry meat supply increased by 14.56 5 from 394.2 thousand tons in 2010 to 451.6 thousand tons in 2015. This positive evolution was determined by the domestic production growth (+16.5%), import growth (+34.3%) and export growth (+58.9%). The share of the domestic production in the poultry meat supply increased from 90.5% in 2010 to 92% in 2015. However, a peak of 96.2% was recorded in 2011 (Table 5).

Table 5. The poultry meat supply in carcass weight (thousand tons) and the share of poultry meat production in Romania in the period 2010-2015 (%)

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2015/2010 %
Poultry meat supply	394.2	396.3	400.1	382.4	437.7	451.6	114.56
Production	356.8	381.6	376.8	365.6	390.4	415.8	116.5
Share of production	90.5	96.2	94.1	95.6	89.1	92.0	-

Source: Own calculation based on the NIS Data base, 2016 [4].

3.6. The poultry meat consumption

The poultry meat consumption increased because of the lower price per kg, but also due to the fact that more consumers are aware that poultry meat is a healthy lean meat, rich in protein and with lower cholesterol than pork.

Table 6. The average poultry meat consumption per inhabitant in Romania in the period 2010-2015 (kg/capita)

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2015/2010 %
Poultry meat consumption	18.2	17.5	18.2	17.5	20.1	22.7	124.7
Share in meat consumption	30.3	31.2	32.9	32.2	34.8	39.1	-

Source: Own calculation based on the NIS Data base, 2016 [4].

In 2015, a Romanian consumed 22.7 kg poultry meat in the average, by 24.7% more than in 2010. As a result, the share of poultry meat in the average meat consumption per inhabitant increased from 30.3% in 2010 to 39.1% in 2015 (Table 6).

3.7. The poultry meat export and import

The poultry meat exported and imported amounts increased because Romania has integrated producing units, mainly the 39 high performance companies which are competitive regarding the modern technologies, daily gain, feed consumption, average live weight at slaughter and slaughter rate per carcass parts, and meat quality. Most of the Romanian poultry growers in the intensive system produce themselves the combined fodder and other ingredients needed to assure a balance diet and high production performance.

The export of poultry meat increased by 58.9% from 58.7 thousand tons in 2010 to 93.3 thousand tons in 2015. However, the imports of poultry meat exceed the exported amounts, affecting the local producers. The import of the poultry meat increased by 34.3% from 96.1 thousand tons in 2010 to 129.1 thousand tons in 2015. Therefore, the poultry meat trade balance is a negative one, and Romania is a net importer of poultry meat (Table 7).

For this reason, the export/import ratio is less than 1. However, the E/I ratio increased by 18% from 0.61 in 2010 to 0.72 in 2015 with some variations up and down across the analyzed period.

Table 7. The poultry meat exports and imports in Romania in the period 2010-2015 (Thousand tons)

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2015/2010 %
Import	96.1	93.7	115.1	100.1	123.3	129.1	134.3
Export	58.7	79.0	91.8	83.3	76.0	93.3	158.9
E/I ratio	0.61	0.84	0.79	0.83	0.62	0.72	118.0

Source: Own calculation based on the NIS Data base, 2016 [4].

3.8. The farm gate price per kilogram live weight

The farm gate price at delivery is still low, varying about lei 3.5-3.7/kg live weight. Many producers are complaining for this small acquisition price because the price for farm inputs increased and are similar to the ones at the EU level.

3.9. Romania's position in the EU regarding the number of slaughtered poultry and weight

Romania is an important poultry meat producer in the EU-28. In 2015, it came on the 7th position in the EU-28 with 213.3 million heads slaughtered poultry and 7,346 thousand tons poultry slaughtered weight.

The first positions in the EU for the number of slaughtered poultry, in the decreasing order, are occupied by France, the United Kingdom, Poland, Germany, Spain and Italy. The first positions for the slaughtered poultry weight, in the descending order, are occupied by Poland, France, the United Kingdom, Germany, Spain and Italy [8].

Conclusions

(1).Romania has a good tradition and high performance in producing poultry meat, keeping the pace with the requirements imposed by the EU and international markets. The industrialization and integration of the poultry sector across the meat chain from producers to consumers assure a high economic efficiency and profitability.

(2).As the domestic production cannot entirely meet the market needs, imports are required. However, the increased imported amounts of poultry meat may not be absorbed by the Romanian consumers and also they deeply affect the Romanian producers, who are obliged to keep stocks and have low deliveries.

(3).Romania's export of poultry meat is continuously developing due to the high quality of poultry meat and the requirements on the EU and international markets, where export price favors the Romanian exporters. The high pressure of the foreign competitors imposes continuous and strong measures to increase production performance (higher daily gain, higher meat quality) and economic efficiency and profitability in the poultry meat sector (profit, profit rate).

(4).To improve economic efficiency in the poultry meat sector are needed: (i) a permanent use of high genetic value meat breeds and hybrids able to get a good gain performance in a shorter period of time, (ii) a corresponding and high nutritive and energetic feeding to assure a higher carcass weight and quality, (iii) a permanent control of the production cost, and (iv) a more intensive marketing to surpass the pressures of the internal and external markets, and to extend the foreign beneficiaries.

REFERENCES

- [1] Audran, X., *EU-28 Poultry and Products Annual, EU-28 Poultry sector to grow again in 2013 and 2014*, Sept.2013, USDA Foreign Agricultural Service
- [2] Dobrescu, M, *Romania Poultry and Products Annual Report 2015*, USDA Foreign Agricultural Service, 2015
- [3] Luca, L., *SWOT Analysis of poultry meat chain in Romania*, Economic Review, No.2, pp.238-246, 2015, <http://revecon.ro/articles/2015-2/2015-2-16.pdf>
- [4] National Institute of Statistics, *Tempo On Line Data base*, 2016, www.insse.ro
- [5] Nistor, E., Bampidis, V., Pet, L., Ciolac, V. *Impact of EU Enlargement on the Romanian Meat Industry*, Scientific Papers: Animal Science and Biotechnologies, Vol.43 (2), pp.364-368, 2010

- [6] Stanciu, S., *Romanian Poultry Meat Sector Analysis*, Proceedings of International Scientific-Practical Conference "Food, Technologies & Health", Agricultural Academy Food Research & Development Institute, pp. 222-228, 2014,
- [7] Van Horne, P.L.M, Bondt, N., *Competitiveness of the EU poultry meat sector*, LEI, Wageningen, 2013
- [8] *** Meat production statistics - Eurostat Statistics Explained, http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Meat_production_statistics

ECOLOGICAL PARAMETERS FOR THE HARMFUL ENTOMOFAUNA FROM FOR THE MILK THISTLE CROPS (*Silybum marianum* L) UNDER CENTER OF MOLDOVA CONDITION

Elena TROTUȘ^{1,2}, Paula-Lucelia URSACHE²

Abstract. *Silybum marianum* L is grown for its fruit (*Fructus cardui* material) containing a specific compound, insoluble in water, with hepatoprotective properties (2.5). The average yield of seeds (fruits) is between 6-12 q/ha, if the harvest is done when 80% of the inflorescences are dry, delaying the harvest involves loss of seeds, which spread easily due to the presence of pappus. Loss of seeds are produced frequently and by a large range of specific and polyphagous pests (3,4,6,7,8,9). It was found that the dangerous entomofauna for the *Silybum marianum* L crops was composed of 28 species of insects that totaled averaged over the entire period between sowing and harvesting (April-July) a total of 702 specimens/sqm. The average density of collected species ranged from 3 specimens/sqm which as totaled at *Anomala solida*, *Decticus verrucivorus*, *Tettigonia viridissima* species and up to 377 specimens/leaf at *Tetranychus urticae*. It was found that 11 species belong to the *Coleoptera* order, six species to *Lepidoptera* order, four species to *Orthoptera* order, three species to *Heteroptera* and *Homoptera* and 1 species to *Acari* order.

Key words: insect, pests, *Silybum marianum*, species.

Introduction

Milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*) is an annual species, herbaceous, with erect stem, hairless leaves, shiny, with a green with white mosaic, sessile and amplexicaule, with terminal veins at the margin ending in spines.

The fruit is a cylindrical achene which ends with a pappus. The species has its origins in the Asian Basin of Mediterranean Sea, where it grows in the spontaneous flora. It is cultivated in Italy, France, Hungary, Poland and others European countries. In our country the most favorable areas for growing are the

¹ Academy of Romania Scientists, Splaiul Independenței 54, 050094, Bucharest, Romania.
Academy of Agriculture and Silviculture Sciences, CS Idr. ing. Stațiunea de Cercetare Dezvoltare Agricolă Secuieni. etrotus@yahoo.com

² As.cercet ing., Stațiunea de Cercetare Dezvoltare Agricolă Secuieni.

Romanian Plain, Timis Plain, Jijiei and Bahlui Plain and in central area of Central Moldavian plateau (2,13).

Silybum marianum L is grown for its fruit (*Fructus cardui material*) containing a specific compound, insoluble in water, with hepatoprotective properties (3,5).

The average yields seed (fruits) are between 6-12 q/ha, if the harvest is done when 80% of the inflorescences are dry, delaying the harvest involves loss of seeds, which spread easily due to the presence of pappus. Loss of seeds are produced frequently and by a large range of specific and polyphagous pests (1,4,6,7,8,9,10,11,12).

The aim of this scientific paper it is to present data regarding the identification of harmful entomofauna from the milk thistle (*Silybum marianum*), under the Central Moldova's condition.

Material and method

The researches were conducted at Secuieni-Neamt unit, located in the Southeast of Neamț County, between the geographical coordinates 26°5' east longitude, 46°5' latitude and at an altitude of 205.7 m above the sea level.

The A.R.D.S Secuieni-Neamț is located in an area characterized with a temperate-continental climate, with the multi-annual average temperature of 8.8°C and the average amount of precipitation of 547 mm.

The milk thistle crops (*Silybum marianum*) were sowed within the Medicinal and Aromatic Plants Laboratory, under conditions of ecological agriculture, and were conducted observation and determination for establishment of the harmful entomofauna.

The biological material gathering was conducted with the help of Barber traps, ground surveys using metric frame 25/25 cm and mowing using entomological net. The collections and determinations were conducted at every ten day, starting from the plant rising phenophase until the harvest phenophase. The collected samples were analyzed in the laboratory at the binocular magnifying glass, determined and separated by species.

For each species were calculated the average density/sqm for the entire plant vegetation period (April-August) and the ecological parameters representative like: **abundance (A)**, **constancy (C)**, **dominance (D)** and **ecological significance index (W)**.

The **abundance** of species (**A%**) represents the number of individuals of a species from the catch in a certain place at a certain time.

The **dominance (D%)** shows the participation percentage of each species in the total catches. It is calculated using the formula.

$$D = \frac{Ax100}{N}$$

D=dominance

A=species abundance

N=the total number of individuals of all species

Depending on the obtained values, the species fall within the following classes of dominance:

D1-subrecedent species $P < 1,0\%$;

D2-recedent species $P = 1,1-2,0\%$;

D3-subdominant species $P = 2,1-5,0\%$;

D4-dominant species $P = 5,1-10,0\%$;

D5-eudominant species $P > 10,1\%$.

The **constancy (C%)** represents the species participation proportion in the realization of the biocenosis structure. It is calculated using the formula:

$$CA = \frac{npA}{Np} \times 100$$

CA=constancy species;

npaA= number of samples in which the A species occurs

Np= total number of collected samples.

Depending on the constancy value, the species are classified as follows.

C1- accidental species(1-25%)

C2- accessories species(25,1-50%)

C3- constant species(50,1-75%)

C4- euconstant species(75,1-100%)

The **index of ecological significance (W%)** represents the relationship between the structural indicator (C) and the productive indicator (D) and is calculated using the formula:

$$W = \frac{Cx Dx 100}{10000}$$

C= species constancy;

D= species dominance.

By the value of the ecological significance index (W), the species fall into three classes, as follows.

W1- accidental species ($W < 10,1\%$)

W2- accessories species ($W = 1,1-5,0\%$)

W3- characteristic species ($W > 5,1\%$)

The ecological parameters of the collected and determined species were calculated and interpreted after the methods presented and published by Simionescu (1983) and Stan (1994).

Results and discussions

After conducting the observations and determinations was found that the dangerous entomofauna for the *Silybum marianum L* crops was composed of 28 species of insects that totaled averaged over the entire period between sowing and harvesting (April-July) a total of 702 specimens/sqm (table1).

The average density of collected species ranged from 3 specimens/sqm which totaled at *Anomala solida*, *Decticus verrucivorus*, *Tettigonia viridissima* species and up to 377 specimens/leaf to *Tetranychus urticae*. (Table 1).

Table 1. The harmful entomofauna from the milk thistle crops (*Silybum marianum L*), under condition of ecological agriculture, Secuieni-Neamț, 2014-2016

	Species	Order	Months/sample/specimens/sqm												Total avr
			April			May			June			July			
			I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
1	<i>Agriotes ustulatus</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	2	3	5	1	0	0	2	1	2	1	0	0	17
2	<i>Agriotes obscurus</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	5
3	<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	0	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	8
4	<i>Melolontha melolontha</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	2	1	2	5	4	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	19
5	<i>Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa</i>	<i>Orthoptera</i>	1	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
6	<i>Opatrum sabulosum</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	0	0	2	3	3	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	13
7	<i>Agrotis segetum</i>	<i>Lepidoptera</i>	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
8	<i>Anomala solida</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
9	<i>Pollyphylla fullo</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
10	<i>Amathes c-nigrum</i>	<i>Lepidoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	3	5	3	1	0	0	0	12
11	<i>Autographa gamma</i>	<i>Lepidoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	2	2	1	3	0	0	0	0	8
12	<i>Vanessa cardui</i>	<i>Lepidoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	2	2	8
13	<i>Loxostege stititalis</i>	<i>Lepidoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
14	<i>Mamestra brassicae</i>	<i>Lepidoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	5	2	0	0	10
15	<i>Phyllotreta nemorum</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	0	3	12	15	10	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	44

Table 1. (continued)

	Species	Order	Months/sample/specimens/sqm												Total avr
			April			May			June			July			
			I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III	
16	<i>Phyllotreta atra</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	0	0	5	3	7	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	17
17	<i>Epicometis hirta</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	15	7	7	40
18	<i>Lytta vesicatoria</i>	<i>Coleoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	4
19	<i>Aphis fabae</i>	<i>Homoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	1*	0	0	0	2*
20	<i>Macrosiphoniella sanborni</i>	<i>Homoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	1*	0	0	2*
21	<i>Graphosoma lineatum</i>	<i>Heteroptera</i>	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	5	4	0	0	14
22	<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i>	<i>Heteroptera</i>	0	0	2	3	0	0	3	4	0	0	0	0	12
23	<i>Eurydema ornata</i>	<i>Heteroptera</i>	0	3	5	7	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	19
24	<i>Decticus verrucivorus</i>	<i>Orthoptera</i>	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
25	<i>Tettigonia viridissima</i>	<i>Orthoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	3
26	<i>Polysarcus denticaudus</i>	<i>Orthoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	2	0	3	1	11
27	<i>Macrosteles sexnotatus</i>	<i>Homoptera</i>	0	0	0	0	4	5	3	1	2	7	9	7	38
28	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>	<i>Acari</i>	0	0	0	0	0	56	64	72	79	84	12	10	377
Total			7	21	41	41	36	86	83	99	111	117	33	27	702

*colony

Following the appearance and evolution of the harmful insects depending on the milk thistle's phenophase, it was noticed that the average density for the period between sowing-emergence phenophase totaled 110 specimens/sqm, followed by 122 specimens/sqm in the leaf rosette formation phenophase, 293 specimens/sqm in the stem elongation – blossom phenophase and 150 specimens in the blooming-seeds formation phenophase (Fig.1).

Fig. 1 – The evolution of the harmful entomofauna depending of the milk thistle phenophase

Analyzing the species collected and determined regarding the systematic inclusion in orders was found that 11 species belong to the *Coleoptera* order, six species to the *Lepidoptera* order, four species to the *Orthoptera* order, three species to the *Heteroptera* and *Homoptera* order and 1 species to the *Acari* order (Table 2).

Table 2 - The collected species belonging to the systemic orders of the Insecta class

crt crt.	Order/number specimens/species											
	<i>Coleoptera</i>		<i>Lepidoptera</i>		<i>Orthoptera</i>		<i>Heteroptera</i>		<i>Homptera</i>		<i>Acari</i>	
	Species	Sp/sqm	Species	sp/sqm	Species	sp/sqm	Species	sp/sqm	Species	Col ex/sqm	Species	sp/leaf
1	<i>Agriotes ustulatus</i>	17	<i>Agrotis segetum</i>	4	<i>Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa</i>	5	<i>Graphosoma lineatum</i>	14	<i>Aphis fabae</i>	2	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>	377
2	<i>Agriotes obscurus</i>	5	<i>Amathes c-nigrum</i>	12	<i>Decticus verrucivorus</i>	3	<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i>	12	<i>Macrosiphoniella sanborni</i>	2		

3	<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>	8	<i>Autographa gamma</i>	8	<i>Tettigonia viridissima</i>	3	<i>Eurydema ornata</i>	19	<i>Macrosteles sexnotatus</i>	38		
4	<i>Melolontha melolontha</i>	19	<i>Vanessa cardui</i>	8	<i>Polysarcus denticaudus</i>	11						
5	<i>Opatrum sabulosum</i>	13	<i>Loxostege sticticalis</i>	5								
6	<i>Anomala solida</i>	3	<i>Mamaestra brassicae</i>	10								
7	<i>Pollyphylla fullo</i>	4										
8	<i>Phyllotreta nemorum</i>	44										
9	<i>Phyllotreta atra</i>	17										
10	<i>Epicometis hirta</i>	40										
11	<i>Lytta vesicatoria</i>	4										
Total	11 species	174	6 species	47	4 species	22	3 species	45	3 species	4 col, 38 sp/sqm	1 species	377

Calculating the share of the collected species, it was found that the *Coleoptera* order reached a maximum share of 39.3% and it was represented by 11 species of harmful insects and the minimum share of 3.6% it is hold by order *Acari* represented by the *Tetranychus urticae* species (Fig 2).

Fig. 2. The order share according to the number of recorded species

Analyzing the number of collected insects, the maximum share of 53.7% it is held by the *Acari* order, with a total number of 377 specimens/leaf and the minimum share of 2.7% it is held by the *Orthoptera* order with 22 specimens/sqm (Fig 3):

Fig. 3. The orders share according to the number of specimens

By calculating the parameters for the species collected was found that:

- **Abundance (A)** ranged between 3 specimens/sqm (*Anomala solida*, *Decticus verrucivorus*, *Tettigonia viridissima*) to 377 specimens/leaf (*Tetranychus urticae*) (Table 3).
- **Dominance (D)** of the collected species ranged from 0.28% (*Aphis fabae*, *Macrosiphoniella sanborni*) to 53.13% (*Tetranychus urticae*) (Table 3).
- The **constancy (C)** index that expresses the continuity of the species occurrence in the analyzed habitat ranged from 16.6% at *Polyphylla fullo*, *Loxostege stitcalis*, *Aphis fabae*, *Macrosiphoniella sanborni*, *Decticus verrucivorus*, *Tettigonia viridissima* species to 66,6% at *Agriotes ustulatus*, *Macrosteles sexnatatus* species;

- **Ecological significance index (W)** which represent the relationship between structural and productive indicator it ranged between 0.05% at the *Macrosiphoniella sanborni*, *Aphis fabae* species and 30.9% at the *Tetranychus urticae* species (table 3).

Table 3.The ecological parameters of the collected species identified in the milk thistle crops (*Silybum marianum* L)

Nr. crt.	Species	Abundance (A)	Dominance (D)	Constancy (C)	Ecological significance index (W)
1	<i>Agriotes ustulatus</i>	17	2.4	66.6	1.6
2	<i>Agriotes obscurus</i>	5	0.7	41.6	0.3
3	<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>	8	1.14	41.6	0.5
4	<i>Melolontha melolontha</i>	19	2.7	50	1.4
5	<i>Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa</i>	5	0.7	25	0.2
6	<i>Opatrum sabulosum</i>	13	1.85	41.6	0.8
7	<i>Agrotis segetum</i>	4	0.57	25.0	0.2
8	<i>Anomala solida</i>	3	0.43	25.0	0.1
9	<i>Pollyphylla fullo</i>	4	0.57	16.6	0.1
10	<i>Amathes c-nigrum</i>	12	1.7	33.3	0.6
11	<i>Autographa gamma</i>	8	1.14	33.3	0.4
12	<i>Vanessa cardui</i>	8	1.14	41.6	0.5
13	<i>Loxostege stiticialis</i>	5	0.7	16.6	0.1
14	<i>Mamaestra brassicae</i>	10	1.40	25.0	0.4
15	<i>Phyllotreta nemorum</i>	44	6.26	50.0	3.13
16	<i>Phyllotreta atra</i>	17	2.42	33.3	0.8
17	<i>Epicomites hirta</i>	40	5.7	33.3	1.9
18	<i>Lytta vesicatoria</i>	4	0.57	25.0	0.1
19	<i>Aphis fabae</i>	2	0.28	16.6	0.05
20	<i>Macrosiphoniella sanborni</i>	2	0.28	16.6	0.05
21	<i>Graphosoma lineatum</i>	14	1.99	41.6	0.83
22	<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i>	12	1.7	33.3	0.6
23	<i>Eurydema ornata</i>	19	2.7	41.6	1.12
24	<i>Decticus verrucivorus</i>	3	0.43	16.6	0.07
25	<i>Tettigonia viridissima</i>	3	0.43	16.6	0.07
26	<i>Polysarcus denticaudus</i>	11	1.56	33.3	0.52
27	<i>Macrosteles sexnotatus</i>	38	5.41	66.6	3.6
28	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>	377	53.13	58.3	30.9
	Total	702	100%	-	-

Regarding the participation percentage of each species in the collected entomofauna at the (calculated after the dominance value) the species collected were classified in the five class of dominance as follows:

- 11 species recorded the participation percentage lower than 1.1% and were classified as subrecedent species;
- 9 species were classified as recedent species;

- 4 species characterized as subdominant species;
- 3 species characterized as dominant species;
- one species belonging to the eudominant class (table 4).

Table 4. Belonging of the collected specie according to the dominance class

No. Crt.	DOMINANCE CLASS				
	Subrecurrent species P < 1.1 %	Recedent species P= 1.2 – 2.0%	Subdominant species P=2.1 – 5.0%	Dominant species P=5.1 - 10%	Eudominant species P> 10.1%
1	<i>Agriotes obscurus</i>	<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>	<i>Agriotes ustulatus</i>	<i>Phyllotreta nemorum</i>	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>
2	<i>Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa</i>	<i>Opatrum sabulosum</i>	<i>Melolontha melolontha</i>	<i>Epicometis hirta</i>	
3	<i>Agrotis segetum</i>	<i>Amathes c-nigrum</i>	<i>Phyllotreta atra</i>	<i>Macrosteles sexnatus</i>	
4	<i>Loxostege stiticalis</i>	<i>Autographa gamma</i>	<i>Eurydema ornata</i>		
5	<i>Lytta vesicatoria</i>	<i>Vanessa cardui</i>			
6	<i>Aphis fabae</i>	<i>Mamaestra brassicae</i>			
7	<i>Macrosiphoniella sanborni</i>	<i>Graphosoma lineatum</i>			
8	<i>Decticus verrucivorus</i>	<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i>			
9	<i>Tettigonia viridissima</i>	<i>Polysarcus denticaudus</i>			
10	<i>Anomala solida</i>				
11	<i>Pollyphylla fullo</i>				
Total	11 species	9 species	4 species	3 species	1 species

Regarding the constancy (C), the collected species were characterized as: 11 accidental species, 15 accessories species, 2 constant species (table 5), and depending the ecological significance index, 21 species were characterized as accidental species, six species as accessories species and one species as characteristic species (Table 6).

Table 5. The harmful entomofauna distribution regarding the constancy class

No. crt.	CONSTANCY CLASS			
	C1 - Accidental species P= 1-25%	C2 –Accessories species P=25.1-50%	C3 – Constant species P= 50.1-75 %	C4 – Euconstant species P= 75.1-100%
1	<i>Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa</i>	<i>Agriotes obscurus</i>	<i>Agriotes ustulatus</i>	-
2	<i>Agrotis segetum</i>	<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>	-
3	<i>Anomala solida</i>	<i>Melolontha melolontha</i>	-	-
4	<i>Pollyphylla fullo</i>	<i>Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa</i>	-	-
5	<i>Loxostege stiticalis</i>	<i>Opatrum sabulosum</i>	-	-
6	<i>Mamestra brassicae</i>	<i>Amathes c-nigrum</i>	-	--
7	<i>Lytta vesicatoria</i>	<i>Autographa gamma</i>	-	-
8	<i>Aphis fabae</i>	<i>Vanessa cardui</i>	-	-
9	<i>Macrosiphoniella sanborni</i>	<i>Phyllotreta nemorum</i>	-	-
10	<i>Decticus verrucivorus</i>	<i>Phyllotreta atra</i>	-	-
11	<i>Tettigonia viridissima</i>	<i>Epicometis hirta</i>	-	-
12	-	<i>Graphosoma lineatum</i>	-	-
13	-	<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i>	-	-
14	-	<i>Eurydema ornata</i>	-	-
15	-	<i>Polysarcus denticaudus</i>	-	-
Total	11 species	15 species	2 species	0 species

Table 6. Belonging of the harmful entomofauna according to the value of ecological significance index (W)

No.crt.	Accidental species W < 1.0%	Accessories species W=1.1 < 5.0%	Characteristic species W 5 > 10%
1	<i>Agriotes obscurus</i>	<i>Agriotes ustulatus</i>	<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>
2	<i>Agriotes lineatus</i>	<i>Melolontha melolontha</i>	

3	<i>Gryllotalpa gryllotalpa</i>	<i>Phyllotreta nemorum</i>	
4	<i>Opatrum sabulosum</i>	<i>Epicometis hirta</i>	
5	<i>Agrotis segetum</i>	<i>Eurydema ornata</i>	
6	<i>Anomala solida</i>	<i>Macrosteles sexnotatus</i>	
7	<i>Pollyphylla fullo</i>		
8	<i>Amathes c-nigrum</i>		
9	<i>Autographa gamma</i>		
10	<i>Vanessa cardui</i>		
11	<i>Loxostege sticticalis</i>		
12	<i>Mamestra brassicae</i>		
13	<i>Phyllotreta atra</i>		
14	<i>Lytta vesicatoria</i>		
15	<i>Aphis fabae</i>		
16	<i>Macrosiphoniella sanborni</i>		
17	<i>Graphosoma lineatum</i>		
18	<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i>		
19	<i>Decticus verrucivorus</i>		
20	<i>Tettigonia viridissima</i>		
21	<i>Polysarcus denticaudus</i>		
Total	21 species	6 species	1 species

Conclusions

- (1) The harmful entomofauna from *Silybum marianum* L. crops is consisted of 28 species that totalized 702 specimens/ sqm for the entire vegetation period.
- (2) The highest density of insects, 293 specimens/sqm was recorded in the stem elongation – blossom phenophases.
- (3) The insects collected were placed in the systematic orders: *Coleoptera*, *Lepidoptera*, *Orthoptera*, *Heteroptera*, *Homoptera* and *Acari*.
- (4) After the number of species, the *Coleoptera* order held the maximum share of 39.3%, and after the number of specimens collected, the maximum share was held by the *Acari* order of 53.7%.
- (5) Depending on the ecological parameters value, the 28 species of collected insects were classified in five dominance class and three constancy class.

(6) Depending on the ecological significance index, 21 species were characterized as accidental species, six species as accessories species and one species as characteristic species.

References

- [1] Bărbulescu Al., 2001, *Achievements and prospects in the diseases and pest control of some field crops*, Ed. GEEA, București
- [2] Bîlteanu Gheorghe, 2001, *Fitotehnie* – Ed. Ceres, București, pp. 528
- [3] Laza A., Racy G., 1975 – *Medicinal and aromatic plants*, Ed Ceres, București
- [4] Perju T. Și colaboratorii, 1988 – *Entomofagii și utilizarea lor în protecția integrată a ecosistemelor agricole*, Ed. Ceres, București
- [5] Popov C., 2003 – *Cercetări cu privire la protecția cerealelor, leguminoaselor pentru boabe, plantelor tehnice și furajere față de agenții patogeni și dăunători efectuate în anul 2002*, Probleme de protecția plantelor, Vol. XXXII, nr. 2, pp. 7-84
- [6] Popov C., Bărbulescu Al., 2007- *50 years of scientific research in the field of plant protection against diseases and pests*. Annals of I.N.C.D. Fundulea, vol. LXXV, Vol. Jubiliar.
- [7] Simionescu I., 1983 – *Fauna României*, Ediția a –III- A, Ed. Albatros, București
- [8] Simionescu V. 1983 - *Lucrări practice de ecologie* - Iasi, Universitatea A.I. Cuza, pp.174-190
- [9] Stan G.,1994 - *Metode statistice cu aplicare în cercetări entomologice*. Buletin de informare, nr.5(2), pp. 113-126
- [10] Teodorescu Georgeta, Roman T., Sumedrea Mihaela, 2003 – *Entomologie horticola, Dăunători specifici și metode de combatere*. Ed. Ceres, București
- [11] Trotuș Elena, Georgeta Pânzaru – 1992 – *Acanthophilus elluta Meig. (Diptera Tephritidae) dăunător al culturilor de gălbenele* – Cercetări Agronomice în Moldova, vol. 4, pp. 139-141
- [12] Trotuș Elena, Doina Dănilă, 2007 – *Data on the specific meadows entomofauna from Siret valley, 45 years of scientific activity at SCDA Secuieni-Neamt*. Anniversary volume, Ed. Ion Ionescu de la Brad, Iași, pp. 175
- [13] Trotuș Elena, Druțu A.C., Găucă C., Popa D. L., Lupu C., Pochișcanu S., Naie Margareta, Leonte A. , 2015 - *Tehnologii de cultivare a unor plante de câmp pentru zona centrală a Moldovei*. Ed. Ion Ionescu de la Brad, Iași, pp. 198.